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SUSTAINABLE FINANCING FOR AIDS IN BURKINA FASO

A prospective assessment of the AIDS financing gap

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Executive summary

The objective of this work is to explore how the Government of Burkina Faso can approach long term financing for AIDS by setting out estimated resource needs against resource availability up till 2020.

Resource needs. We estimate the financial resources needed for the AIDS Response in Burkina Faso till 2020 taking as a basis the resource needs estimates from the 'Model for Estimating Resource Needs for Prevention, Care and Mitigation' developed in 2009 by John Stover, Lori Bollinger (Futures Group International) and Andrew Boule and Susan Cleary (University of Cape Town, South Africa). We extrapolate the resource needs for each programme separately using a growth trend, to 2020. The total resource needs stand at about US\$ 86 million in 2020. As with all projections the results need to be interpreted with caution. The major caveat is that the projection is path-dependent on the period 2010-2015.

Macro economic outlook. The estimate of resource availability is supported by a macroeconomic framework ensuring consistency in the projections and capturing some of the interactions between HIV and AIDS spending and the economy. The approach adopts a simple financial programming framework. It takes as a starting point the tables published on Burkina's macroeconomic performance by the IMF. Doing so it is possible to condense the forecasting of the economy, and its various sectors, to a handful of key assumptions.

Burkina Faso suffered a slight reduction in the growth rate in 2009, but real GDP growth returned to 5.2% in 2010 and growth is expected to continue. Despite the global downturn, Burkina Faso recorded a budget deficit of only 2.3% in 2009, though this has risen to 5.4% in 2010. In the medium term growth will continue at slightly increased rates, an average of 5.8% per annum in 2011-2013. Tax revenues are expected to increase modestly to reach 15.7% of GDP by 2013, and the fiscal deficit is expected to decline slightly, averaging 3.6% of GDP in 2011-2013. In the long term GDP growth is assumed to be 5.6% per annum, and tax revenue (excluding any new measures for HIV/AIDS) is assumed to remain at 15.7% of GDP. Budget support and non-HIV project grants are expected to remain constant in US\$ terms from 2015 onwards. Following the recent trend, government current expenditure is assumed to be constant at 11.7% of GDP, excluding interest costs.

Resource availability – baseline scenario. It is within this macro economic projection that we situate the available resources for HIV. We take as a starting point AIDS expenditure in 2008 such as reported in the NASA (National AIDS Spending Assessment). For international finance we assume that external flows to Burkina Faso remain constant in US\$ terms through to 2020. For domestic public financing we assume that the same proportion of government expenditure is allocated to HIV expenditure as that of 2009. In 2009, 1.3% of discretionary current expenditures were budgeted for HIV/AIDS and this assumption is continued through to 2020. For private sources of funds we disregard out-of-pocket expenditure, as this source of funding does either not contribute to covering estimated HIV resource needs, or, where it may do, is an undesirable source of funding, as it is inequitable and hinders access to needed services.

AIDS financing gap – baseline scenario. Under a baseline scenario, using the assumptions above, the financing gap for HIV/AIDS is estimated at CFAF 7.9 billion in 2010 declining to CFAF 1.3 billion in 2020, which is 0.18% of GDP in 2010 and 0.01% of GDP in 2020. This implies that relatively small increases in resources can cover the resource needs of HIV/AIDS in Burkina Faso, and this increasingly so over time.

We then explore a number of alternative financing options that have the potential to increase the fiscal space for HIV and AIDS expenditure in Burkina Faso.

Public sector mainstreaming. The HIV/AIDS response in Burkina Faso is based on a multisectoral approach and each line ministry, decentralised unit, government agency and public association is obliged to include a budget line for activities to combat HIV/AIDS, including prevention and treatment of staff members who are HIV positive. Each public agency is free to determine how much it spends on AIDS but in reality this is very low and not more than 0.1% of expenditure (excluding those Ministries that have HIV/AIDS in their mandate such as the Ministry of Health). A policy of internal mainstreaming, broadly spoken these are workplace programme for public agency staff, where 1% of the wage bill is devoted to HIV/AIDS would generate an additional FCA 5 billion in 2020. If ministries devote 1% of their budget allocation to external mainstreaming, which are activities targeted by the public agency to their target group (e.g. students for the Ministry of Education) this would yield another FCA 5.3 billion in 2020. Taken together a full-fledged mainstreaming policy would generate more than FCA 10 billion, which is almost 25% of the resource needs in 2020.

Decentralisation. Contributions for HIV/AIDS by decentralised authorities is grounded in a rationale very similar to public sector mainstreaming: local authorities are well placed to understand the needs of the population, have an explicit mandate to address those needs and should be able to improve the effectiveness of public spending. The process of decentralisation in Burkina Faso started in 1995 and decentralised units are also required to implement AIDS activities. If decentralised units spend 1% of their revenue for recurrent spending (except for higher level grants) towards HIV and AIDS in the 2020 this would generate an additional CFA 0.58 billion in 2020.

Private sector contributions. Private businesses and companies are seen as an integral part of the fight against the HIV/AIDS pandemic, and the Strategic Framework recognises their role. Businesses are often motivated to engage in HIV activities because the epidemic increases the cost of care in their workforce, and decreases its productivity. The large majority of formal businesses in Burkina Faso is too small to consider designing a policy for: the transaction costs to police the policy would be too high. However, if companies of more than 9 employees would be obliged to implement a workplace programme with peer education, condom distribution and STI treatment, then an additional CFA 0.1 billion could be raised by 2020.

Airtime tax. In a small number countries, Gabon and Kenya for example, the government considers introducing a levy on mobile phone airtime as one means of overcoming the national HIV/AIDS financing gap. This levy has been faced with criticism primarily due to the distortionary effects on the mobile phone industry and the disproportionate burden that it places on the poor who increasingly rely on mobile phone coverage as a means of communication. Currently there is no specific levy on mobile phones in Burkina Faso. Value Added Tax, which is governed by article 318 to 386 of the Tax Code, is applied on all transactions at a uniform rate of 18%. Corporation tax

which is applied to industrial, commercial and agricultural corporations is levied on net profits at the rate of 30%. There are three main mobile phone operators in Burkina: Telmob, Telcel and Zain (to become Bharti Airtel as of October 2010). Telemob is the market leader with about 45% of the market share. Mobile phone market penetration in Burkina Faso is extremely low which means that the next few years may see an expansion of mobile phone coverage in the country. Ideally calculations of the expected revenue from this levy should be based on minutes of airtime sold. But since this data is not available, we base our estimations on the expected annual turnover. In order to move from these rather summary data to an estimate of possible resource mobilisation for HIV/AIDS we have to make a number of further assumptions. First, we assume that only half of total turnover by mobile phone operators is from airtime. This is probably an underestimate. Second, we envisage the application of an additional 5% airtime tax, which is the lower limit of what is currently applied in some countries in Eastern Africa. We take the lower limit because heavily taxing airtime faces increasing criticism. Based on these assumptions an airtime levy of 5% could generate an additional FCFA 10.2 billion in 2020.

Flight tax. Revenue generated through the collection of a tax on flight departures represents a new opportunity to raise money for HIV/AIDS. This type of levy is seen as having no distortionary effects on the demand for air travel, is progressive, i.e. not burdening the poorer populations, and cheap to collect. There is widespread international experience with flight tax, also for AIDS, through UNITAID. There is currently no tax on flights in Burkina Faso for the purpose of funding the fight against HIV/AIDS. Based on historic growth patterns we estimate that the number of domestic passengers increases by 2%, regional passengers increase by 8% and international passengers by 4% per year up to 2020. Although many different scenarios are possible, we opt for a zero levy on domestic flights, \$20 on regional flights and \$30 on international flights. Doing so would generate CFA 3.6 billion by 2020.

Social Health Insurance. The Government of Burkina Faso has made a high level commitment to expanding social health protection in the country. A Permanent Secretariat is tasked with preparing the ground for this ambitious project. We use the working hypotheses of the Permanent Secretariat to estimate the potential contribution of such a scheme by calculating the increase in premium necessary to cover the ARV costs in the pool of members covered by the scheme. We find that on average, in the period 2010 to 2020 it would be necessary to increase the premium with between CFA 287 and 405. However, as the premium differs per membership segment (formal sector workers pay more than informal worker, for example), the share of the premium to cover ARV only is almost as high as 20% for informal sector premiums. If the scheme would be set up and reach near universal coverage by 2020, and additional CFA 4.2 billion could be mobilised to cover ARV costs. However, given the uncertainty surrounding the start date and coverage expansion of the scheme, and whether it would be appropriate to include ARV in the benefit package, we do not take these estimations forward in the remainder of the analysis.

Additional borrowing. Although there are no universal rules that set a limit on how much debt a country can incur, the net present value of Burkina's debt, as well as the debt stock expressed as a share of GDP suggests there is room for additional borrowing. While this would be a major source of resources for HIV and AIDS, this report advises against this option for the following reasons. Burkina Faso is classified as being at high risk of debt distress under the IMF-World Bank Debt Sustainability Framework and any

additional borrowing to finance HIV expenditure, particularly borrowing from external sources, will exacerbate this situation. Second, even if it could be argued that spending on HIV and AIDS is an investment, in that it reduces future costs and improves growth, by increasing longevity and reducing infections, at least part of the expenditures discussed here should be considered as current. This makes the case for borrowing less convincing. Thirdly, there can be negative macroeconomic consequences of increasing the government deficit as it may increase inflation and “crowd out” the private sector by reducing lending, which can have a negative consequence on growth. Additional borrowing should therefore only be considered as an option of ‘last resort’.

AIDS financing gap – revisited. After examining the potential contributions from alternative sources of funding, it is now possible to re-examine the total resources available for HIV. This is achieved by combining the baseline resources with the innovative sources. The table below provides an overview. New borrowing and social health insurance are not included.

CFA billion	Baseline Total	Internal mainstreaming	External mainstreaming	Workplace Programs	Airtime tax	Flight tax	Decentralisation	Total Resources
2008	25.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.2
2009	27.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.3
2010	27.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.8
2011	28.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.4
2012	29.1	0.9	0.9	0.1	4.2	2.3	0.3	37.8
2013	29.8	2.0	2.1	0.1	4.5	2.4	0.4	41.3
2014	30.6	3.2	3.4	0.1	5.0	2.6	0.4	45.2
2015	31.5	3.4	3.6	0.1	5.6	2.7	0.4	47.4
2016	32.5	3.7	3.9	0.1	6.3	2.9	0.5	49.9
2017	33.5	4.0	4.2	0.1	7.2	3.1	0.5	52.6
2018	34.7	4.3	4.5	0.1	8.2	3.2	0.5	55.6
2019	35.9	4.6	4.9	0.1	9.2	3.4	0.6	58.8
2020	37.2	5.0	5.3	0.1	10.2	3.6	0.6	62.0

The innovative sources grow in importance over time, starting at CFAF 8.7 billion in 2012 and reaching CFAF 24.8 billion by 2020. Some alternative financing sources are more promising than others. For example the effort to mobilise resources from ‘decentralisation’ and ‘workplace programmes’ may not be worth the transaction cost, especially not in light of the potential of the other alternative sources. The financing gap in the baseline scenario is estimated at Kw 7.9 billion in 2010 declining to Kw 1.3 billion in 2020. The resources that could be mobilised over the entire period through alternative sources (CFAF 155.6 billion) outstrip the cumulative resource gap over the same period (CFAF 40 billion). However, the return from alternative sources is lowest in when they are set up, and mature over time. However, the AIDS financing gap is highest in the short run, tapering off towards 2020. Therefore, depending on how quickly the alternative sources can be tapped into, the risk is real that a short term financing gap will remain.

Efficiency. In 2007 the efficiency of the Burkina Faso AIDS response stood at 33%, compared to an average of 48% in a pool of 68 countries analysed using Data Envelope Analysis. In that same year some countries were working on the production frontier achieving an efficiency of 100%. Although the causes for this relative inefficiency deserve more analysis, it is worth pointing out that the management of the Response is comparatively expensive, 22% compared to 14% of total resources for AIDS were devoted to coordination in 2008. We also found that whereas Burkina pays a competitive price for first line ARV, there is room to buy cheaper second line ARV. It is likely that there are other sources of inefficiencies, and not all of them easy to remedy. Based on the trend from 2002 to 2007 in Burkina's efficiency score, we estimate that the efficiency of the Response stood at 52% in 2010. We then assume that it is possible to reach 100% efficiency in 2017. If these efficiency gains are made, significantly less resources are needed to deliver the AIDS Response. Even under the baseline scenario, without additional sources of funds, the AIDS financing gap could be closed by 2013 with efficiency gains. However, it is important that the sources of inefficiency are fully understood before it can be asserted that efficiency gains can effectively be achieved.

Conclusion. Our analysis is reasonably optimistic about the prospects of sustainable financing for AIDS in Burkina Faso. We find a moderate AIDS financing gap under a baseline scenario, which, importantly, assumes that development partners maintain their aid at the current nominal level till 2020. But we also identified a host of promising and sustainable alternative sources of funds, which can create additional fiscal space to finance AIDS expenditure. There are also strong indications that the AIDS Response in Burkina Faso is not fully efficient and that if the causes of inefficiency are identified and addressed, more can be achieved with fewer resources. This then in turn suggests that Burkina Faso is able to successfully develop a sustainable AIDS financing strategy, with AIDS expenditure increasingly covered by domestically generated resources. Important support from development partners, especially in the short term, will, however, remain necessary to avoid having to scale back the AIDS Response.

Limitations. While this analysis is encouraging it needs to be qualified. First, it is important to ascertain the resource needs estimates, especially for the years after 2015, as these estimates are but an extrapolation of the resource needs in the period 2010 – 2015. Second, given that the resource needs and available resources are calculated separately it is not guaranteed that the available resources will be targeted at the needs as identified, as some revenue sources will be earmarked for certain areas (prevention, research, treatment, management, etc.) and activities (ARVs, workplace programmes, IEC, etc.). It is not enough to generate additional resources; it is also important to develop the governance and resource allocation mechanisms to make sure that these resources are targeted at the priority interventions. Third, there is a high degree of uncertainty when looking at macroeconomic variables over this time horizon. This would be the case even where a complex economic model is used, but is particularly true for the analysis presented in this report. As such, the macroeconomic data included in this document should be seen as “scenarios”, rather than formal forecasts or projections. Finally, resource needs and gap estimates change over time in light of new information and changes to the structure and scale of interventions. The findings of this study are therefore but a starting point for discussion among the key stakeholders on the validity of resource needs requirements and the different paths to covering any financing gap.

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1 Rationale

Up until recently, scarcity of resources was not a priority in the global AIDS policy fora. Indeed, exceptionalism was successfully defended on multiple grounds (Peter Piot 2008). In a breach of conventional thinking about sustainable financing for development the Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis call for proposals for example noted: "Applicants are not required to demonstrate financial self-sufficiency for the targeted interventions by the end of the proposal term."¹

During the late 1990s and early 2000s a global political momentum to 'end poverty' gave rise to two ambitious ventures of international development assistance. The Millennium Development Project devotes one goal specifically to HIV and AIDS, and the Global Fund to fight AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis was set up with the single purpose to make progress on three of the most important public health crises worldwide.

However, the political commitments have not fully materialised and ODA has increased by less than anticipated since the UN Conference on Financing for Development in Monterrey, in 2002². In the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis many low and middle income countries wonder if, and how, donor countries will maintain the aid levels they committed to.

Meanwhile, the success of ART programmes has contributed to the understanding that AIDS programmes and particularly ARV treatment create a life-long entitlement of HIV positive citizens on their governments. Governments, especially those in high HIV prevalence countries, therefore bear an important responsibility to meet these needs.

The objective of this work is to explore how the Government of Burkina Faso can approach long term financing for AIDS. We start from the resource needs to finance the Response, which we project up to 2020. We then extrapolate over the same period the available resources in a 'baseline' scenario that does not consider any additional financing sources, nor any major changes in existing sources. This yields a first 'baseline resource gap', the difference between resource need and resource availability. We then consider a number of strategies that can generate additional resources for AIDS. These were identified through discussions with stakeholders in Burkina Faso, including the Ministry of Finance. This allows us to compute a second 'resource gap' which now takes into account the additional resources. We then examine the efficiency of Burkina Faso's AIDS Response and whether savings can be made in the resource needs. In a last section we carry out some sensitivity analysis to provide upper and lower boundaries around the estimated extrapolations.

¹ Gorik Ooms, Wim Van Damme, Brook K Baker, Paul Zeitz and Ted Schreker (2008). "The 'diagonal' approach to Global Fund financing: a cure for the broader malaise of health systems?" Globalization and Health 4(6).

² Global development finance (2008). Financial flows to developing countries: recent trends and prospects, The World Bank Group.

2 Resource needs 2011 - 2020

We estimate the financial resources needed for the AIDS Response in Burkina Faso till 2020. We take as a basis the resource needs estimates from the 'Model for Estimating Resource Needs for Prevention, Care and Mitigation' developed in 2009 by John Stover, Lori Bollinger (Futures Group International) and Andrew Boule and Susan Cleary (University of Cape Town, South Africa). This model is driven by population needs, combined with coverage targets and unit costs per intervention area. It estimates resource needs for four programmes: prevention, treatment, mitigation and coordination. We extrapolate the resource needs for each programme separately using a growth trend ($y=a+bx^2$). This allows each programme to expand following its own specific growth rate. We then sum up the cost per programme to obtain the total projected resource need for the period 2016 – 2020. This provides the estimate shown in the figure below.

Figure 2.1 Resource needs 2011 - 2020

The total resource needs stand at about US\$ 86 million in 2020. As with all projections the results need to be interpreted with caution. The major caveat is that the projection is path-dependent on the period 2010-2015. An alternative approach would have been to expand the original resource needs estimate model, which is based on population need and would allow to adapt coverage targets.

The resource needs thus obtained are used as a benchmark throughout this work. However, the resource availability is estimated independently. This allows alternative resource needs estimates to be set out against the in this work projected resource availability, and thus produce alternative 'resource gaps'.

3 Macro economic context

Underlying any assessment of resource availability is the macroeconomic context within which the HIV/AIDS effort operates. The analysis presented in this work is supported by a macroeconomic framework ensuring consistency in the projections and capturing some of the interactions between HIV and AIDS spending and the economy.

This section sets out the approach taken to the macroeconomic framework. We start with a description of how the framework is developed and apply it to Burkina Faso. The short, medium and long term macroeconomic prospects are discussed and their implications for the various streams of HIV and AIDS financed are presented.

3.1 Theoretical approach

A fuller description of the framework used for the macroeconomic analysis is presented in Annex A. This section provides an outline of the approach. The section starts by describing the overall macroeconomic framework and then goes on to describe how HIV/AIDS flows and expenditures interact with the framework.

3.1.1 Macroeconomic framework

The starting point for the macroeconomic framework is the tables published on Burkina Faso's macroeconomic performance by the IMF. These tables are produced in a standard format for all countries as part of the IMF's Article IV surveillance activities. The standard IMF documents include five tables that are replicated in the macroeconomic framework used for this analysis. These are:

Table 1: Selected Economic Indicators, containing summary data from the real, fiscal, monetary and external sectors.

Tables 2 & 3: Fiscal Operations of Central Government, describing the government budget and its financing.

Table 4: Monetary Accounts, showing the paths of broad money, net foreign assets and net domestic assets.

Table 5: Balance of Payments, including indicators on gross international reserves.

The framework expands these tables to produce data for the following sectors of the economy:

- Real Sector, including projections for real GDP growth and GDP deflator.
- Fiscal Sector, including projections for domestic revenue, expenditure, grants and deficit financing.
- Monetary Sector, including projections for credit to the private sector.
- External Sector, including projections for imports, exports, exchange rate and gross international reserves.

Though not a sector in its own right, the framework also includes a sheet for central government debt, including projections for both the domestic and external debt stock.

The approach adopts a simple financial programming framework. Financial programming frameworks can support macroeconomic analysis by ensuring consistency between various inter-related sets of variables. The framework ensures consistency between the sectors in two ways.

First, where a variable is included in more than one sector, it is linked across sectors to ensure a consistent approach. For example, exports appear in both the balance of payments (external sector) and the national accounts (real sector). In this case, assumptions are made that produces projections for exports in the external sector. These projections are then linked across to ensure the same data is used for exports in the real sector. Table 1 in Annex A describes the detailed linkages between each sector.

Second, consistency within each sector is also ensured by use of a residual. Each sector can be described by an accounting identity which must always be true. For example, in the real sector, total GDP must be equal to the sum of its components. Therefore, if projections are produced for all but one of the variables in the accounting identity, the remaining variable – the “residual” – must be set at a level to ensure that the identity is true.

For example, in the real sector, projections are produced for total GDP, imports, exports, government consumption, government investment and private investment. In order to ensure that the components of GDP are equal to total GDP, the final component – private consumption – must be set at a level equal to total GDP less the other components of GDP.

The following describes the accounting identities for each sector:

Real Sector: $GDP = Consumption + Investment + Exports - Imports$

Fiscal Sector: $Total Revenue - Total Expenditure = Net Borrowing$

Monetary Sector: $Net Foreign Assets + Net Domestic Assets = Broad Money$

External Sector: $Current Account + Capital Account + Financial Account = Change in Official Reserve Assets$

Using the above framework, it is possible to condense the forecasting of the economy, and its various sectors to just a handful of key assumptions. Using these assumptions, the linkages and identities described above it is possible to project a range of macroeconomic variables and indicators into the future.

The framework therefore operates by retaining the IMF projections for the short and medium term (until 2013) and makes a number of high level assumptions for key macroeconomic variables over the long term. These assumptions are based upon an extrapolation of the medium term IMF projections and an analysis of the available information on the Burkina Faso economy.

3.1.2 Incorporating HIV and AIDS resources

HIV and AIDS resources can be expressed as revenues or expenditures. It is important to be clear on the distinction to avoid double-counting. For example, a grant from a donor would be included as a revenue but may also be counted as an expenditure by the government. Table 3.1 shows the HIV and AIDS resources incorporated into the macroeconomic framework and the sectors that they are linked directly to.

Table 3.1 HIV and AIDS Resource Flows in the Macroeconomic Framework

Resource Flow	Sector Linkages
Revenues	
External project grants included in the budget	Fiscal, External
External project grants not included in the budget	None
External project loans	Fiscal, External, (Debt)
Tax and non-tax revenues collected by the government and earmarked for HIV and AIDS	Fiscal
Domestic borrowing by the government and earmarked for HIV and AIDS	Fiscal, (Debt)
Expenditures	
Government Current Expenditure	Fiscal
Expenditure by external project grants not included in the budget	None
Expenditure by private individuals and companies	Real

These resources are integrated into the appropriate sectors of the macroeconomic framework. This ensures consistency in both the macroeconomic projections and the HIV expenditure projections in two ways.

First, those resources that are determined exogenously (either through external factors or by policy decisions) are linked to the macroeconomic framework so that changes in these variables have a macroeconomic impact. For example, higher grants from external donors may (i) increase government expenditure in the fiscal sector and (ii) increase the change in official reserves in the external sector (amongst other effects). Equally, a decision to increase borrowing to finance HIV will (i) increase government expenditure

and the deficit in the fiscal sector and (ii) by higher interest payments on that debt, further increase the deficit in future years (again amongst other effects).

Second, HIV and AIDS resources can be linked to macroeconomic variables to model their size under different scenarios. For example, external grants and loans will be converted into local currency via the exchange rate and domestic resources can be linked to GDP growth to see how they change under different scenarios for economic growth.

Using the framework above, it is then possible to insert different assumptions for key macroeconomic variables and HIV and AIDS financing sources to examine scenarios for HIV and AIDS expenditure into the future. These scenarios can be supported by various indicators to assess the plausibility of the scenario (e.g. is the share of HIV/AIDS expenditure of GDP excessive?) and its macroeconomic stability (e.g. is government debt sustainable? Is the balance of payments stable?).

3.2 Application in Burkina Faso

The following section applies this framework to Burkina Faso, in doing so, describes the macroeconomic context within which the HIV/AIDS pandemic must be addressed. By developing the macroeconomic context in this manner, it is possible to quantify the size of the available resources under both a baseline scenario and one with alternative funding mechanisms (explored later in this paper). The macroeconomic performance of the country also places an inherent cap on any domestically generated resources for HIV and AIDS and therefore is important for determining the plausibility of the total HIV/AIDS funding availability identified in this report.

This section describes the composition of the Burkina Faso economy and its performance in the short term. It goes on to look at the IMF projections for the medium term and applies the framework described above to paint a scenario for longer term macroeconomic performance.

3.2.1 Short Term

The key exports of the Burkina Faso economy are cotton, gold and livestock. Gold has become increasingly important in recent years, with exports having risen from US\$ 35m in 2007 to US\$ 698m in 2010. Burkina Faso suffered a slight reduction in the growth rate in 2009, but real GDP growth returned to 5.2% in 2010 and growth is expected to continue.

Despite the global downturn, Burkina Faso recorded a budget deficit of only 2.3% in 2009, though this has risen to 5.4% in 2010. Government revenue has been rising since 2008 and government has increased capital expenditure, whilst current expenditure remains constant (as a share of GDP). Controlled fiscal policy, together with earlier debt relief, have left debt stocks at relatively low levels with total central government debt at 28% of GDP. However, due to its high proportion of external debt, Burkina Faso is vulnerable and classified as high risk of debt distress. After large price increases in 2008, the central bank has reduced inflation to 0.2% and intends to retain it at 2% in coming years.

Burkina Faso's exports are highly dependent on the cotton and, more recently, gold industries. The current account deficit is 5.2% of GDP and expected to increase in the short term. However, gross international reserves, a key indicator of the country's ability to pay for imports, are sufficient and in excess of three months of imports.

3.2.2 Medium Term

The starting point for the medium term projections are those produced by the IMF. These envisage that growth will continue at slightly increased rates in the coming years, an average of 5.8% per annum in 2011-2013. This is based on a continued increase in copper production and sustained copper prices.

Tax revenues are expected to increase modestly to reach 15.7% of GDP by 2013. Tax revenues as a share of GDP have increased steadily from 12.1% of GDP in 2008. This demonstrates the possibility of raising taxes in the longer term, and is discussed further below.

Although non-tax revenue and grants decline slightly by 2013, total revenue and grants are broadly constant. Total government expenditure is expected to increase modestly over the period to 25.6% of GDP in 2013. The increase in expenditure is due to a rise in capital expenditure to 13.2% of GDP in 2013.

As a consequence of the above, the fiscal deficit is decline slightly, averaging 3.6% of GDP in 2011-2013. The budget is entirely financed from external sources, allowing net repayments of domestic sources. Total public debt will rise by a modest amount to reach 30.6% of GDP by 2013.

In the external sector, the current account deficit is expected to worsen to reach 7.6% of GDP in 2013. Burkina Faso has relatively little foreign direct investment and portfolio investment and this is expected to continue. Accordingly, there is a modest reduction in reserves in each year and gross international reserves are expected to decline slightly to 5.7 months of imports.

In the monetary sector, inflation is expected to remain around 2% up to 2013. The velocity of money is expected to remain constant at 3.3. Credit to the private sector is expected to rise to around 19% of GDP by 2013.

3.2.3 Long Term

Projecting economic variables over the long term is necessarily a matter of speculation. This is particularly the case with the exercise being undertaken here, where macroeconomic figures are required as far into the future as 2020. The following sections set out the assumptions used in the macroeconomic framework, which in turn is used to produce the scenarios for HIV and AIDS expenditure discussed below.

GDP growth is assumed to be 5.6% per annum, in line with the four year average for GDP data provide by the IMF for 2010-2013³. This is a slight reduction on the 6.2% growth projected by the IMF for 2013. External demand for gold is expected to remain

³ A four year average is used due to the exceptional nature of the financial crisis in 2008 and 2009.

strong and exports of gold will remain at around 10% of GDP. The GDP deflator is assumed to be 2% reflecting the efforts of the central bank to control inflation.

Tax revenue (excluding any new measures for HIV/AIDS) is assumed to remain at 15.7% of GDP, in line with the modest increase expected by the IMF through to 2013. Budget support and non-HIV project grants are expected to remain constant in US\$ terms from 2015 onwards.

Following the recent trend, government current expenditure is assumed to be constant at 11.7% of GDP, excluding interest costs. This does not include additional expenditures associated with the HIV and AIDS mechanisms described above. Government capital expenditure is assumed to be 12.6% of GDP in 2014, but declines in subsequent years to ensure the deficit remains constant at around 3% of GDP.

The exchange rate is expected to appreciate mildly at 0.6% per annum. This reflects the average of IMF projections for 2010 to 2013 and the importance of the growing gold exports. The trade deficit is assumed to be constant at 3% of GDP and the current account deficit declines slight each year from its 2013 peak of 7.6% of GDP. In the monetary sector, the velocity of money is assumed to be constant at 3.3.

The following sections describe how the various resource mobilisation mechanisms for HIV and expenditures are impacted by the scenario set out above. In Section 8, we carry out a sensitivity analysis and examine the impact of variations in these assumptions on the resources available for HIV.

4 Baseline scenario

In this section we estimate the available resources for HIV under the baseline scenario (i.e. without any additional resources). Drawing on the resource needs set out above, we then examine the AIDS financing gap – the difference between the resource needs and the available resources. The baseline scenario applies conservative assumptions for extrapolation of the available resources through to 2020.

4.1 Financial resources available

Table 4.1 presents the available resources for HIV/AIDS in 2008, as included in the NASA. This table shows that the majority of resources came from international donors and a total of CFAF 25 billion were available in 2008.

Table 4.1 Resources for HIV/AIDS Expenditure 2008 (CFAF)

Source de financement	Agent de financement public	Agent de financement privé	Agent de financement Extérieur	Total en F.CFA	Total en USD
Fonds publics	5 756 344 071	2 555 000	0	5 758 899 071	12 123 998
Budget de l'Etat	1 596 605 759	2 555 000	0	1 599 160 759	3 366 654
Prêts remboursables	4 114 602 792	0	0	4 114 602 792	8 662 322
Autres fonds publics non classifiés ailleurs (n.c.a.)	45 135 520	0	0	45 135 520	95 022
Fonds privés	0	2 359 473 763	0	2 359 473 763	4 967 313
Institutions et entreprises à but lucratif	0	59 681 342	0	59 681 342	125 645
Fonds des ménages	0	2 287 748 005	0	2 287 748 005	4 816 312
Institutions à but non lucratif (autres que l'assurance sociale)	0	12 044 416	0	12 044 416	25 357
Fonds internationaux	11 190 154 004	1 152 096 270	4 704 106 306	17 046 356 580	35 887 066
Contributions bilatérales directes	2 438 411 256	60 667 977	2 357 109 078	4 856 188 311	10 223 554
Organismes multilatéraux administrant des subventions pré-affectées	8 165 854 810	0	1 723 390 755	9 889 245 565	20 819 464
Organisations et fondations internationales à but non lucratif	585 887 938	1 091 428 293	623 606 473	2 300 922 704	4 844 048
Total en F.CFA	16 946 498 075	3 514 125 033	4 704 106 306	25 164 729 414	52 978 378
Total en USD	35 676 838	7 398 158	9 903 382	52 978 378	
%	67,34%	13,96%	18,69%	100,00%	

Source: NASA (2008)

In order to derive estimates of resource availability we make a number of assumptions for the two sources of financing namely international and public domestic resources.

For international financing we assume that external flows to Burkina Faso remain constant in US\$ terms through to 2020. The figure chosen is the 2008 external HIV and AIDS flows to Burkina Faso, as presented above. For the purposes of the macroeconomic framework, the flows are divided into those which pass through the government budget (known as “on-budget”) and those which are “off-budget”. The distinction is necessary as on-budget grants will impact on the size of government expenditure, whereas off-budget grants do not. The on- and off-budget grants also pass through the balance of payments in different ways.

For domestic public financing we assume the same proportion of government expenditure is allocated to HIV expenditure as that of 2008. In 2009, 1.3% of discretionary current expenditures were budgeted for HIV/AIDS and this assumption is continued through to 2020. In this case, discretionary expenditure is determined by taking total current expenditure and excluding interest costs and externally financed HIV expenditure. Interest costs are a government obligation and clearly cannot be diverted to HIV expenditure. Externally financed HIV expenditure is the same as on-budget expenditure, discussed above, and is therefore removed to avoid double counting.

Clearly, the above assumptions are linked to the macroeconomic framework. External flows must be converted using the exchange rate and domestic flows will be determined by nominal GDP growth and the size of current expenditure as a share of GDP. In this way, the macroeconomic framework ensures a consistent underpinning to these independent assumptions.

4.2 AIDS financing gap

Using the information above, Table 4.2 extrapolates the resources available from public, private and international sources through to 2020. As can be seen, the resources in 2008 represented 0.8% of GDP which decline to 0.4% of GDP by 2020.

Table 4.2 Baseline Resources and Financing Gap for HIV/AIDS 2008 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	Public sources	Private sources	International sources	Total	as % of GDP	Resource needs	Financing Gap	as % of GDP
2008	5.8	2.4	17.0	25.2	0.7%	25.5	0.3	0.01%
2009	6.3	2.5	18.5	27.3	0.7%	31.9	4.6	0.12%
2010	6.7	2.7	18.4	27.8	0.6%	35.7	7.9	0.18%
2011	7.2	2.9	18.3	28.4	0.6%	32.7	4.3	0.09%
2012	7.7	3.2	18.2	29.1	0.6%	33.2	4.1	0.08%
2013	8.4	3.4	18.0	29.8	0.6%	33.5	3.6	0.07%
2014	9.0	3.7	17.9	30.6	0.5%	34.1	3.5	0.06%
2015	9.7	4.0	17.8	31.5	0.5%	34.7	3.2	0.05%
2016	10.5	4.3	17.7	32.5	0.5%	34.8	2.3	0.03%
2017	11.3	4.6	17.6	33.5	0.5%	35.4	1.9	0.03%
2018	12.1	5.0	17.5	34.7	0.4%	36.3	1.6	0.02%
2019	13.1	5.4	17.4	35.9	0.4%	37.3	1.4	0.02%
2020	14.1	5.8	17.3	37.2	0.4%	38.5	1.3	0.01%

Figure 4.1 Resource Needs and Available Resources - Baseline, 2008 - 2020

Comparing the available resources with the resource needs presented earlier, we see that there is a shortfall in funding (known as the “financing gap”). This short fall peaks at CFAF 7.9 billion in 2010 and declines to CFAF 1.3 billion in 2020. However, as a share of GDP, the gap is relatively modest. The remainder of this report examines options to fill this gap by looking at alternative sources of finance.

Figure 4.2 Financing Gap – Baseline and Innovative Sources, 2008 - 2020

5 Alternative sources of funding

The financing gap under the baseline scenario stands at between 0.12% and 0.01% of GDP between 2012 and 2020 (see previous section). In this section we explore a range of alternative financing options that increase the fiscal space for HIV/AIDS expenditures.

The mechanisms explored in the case of Burkina Faso include:

1. Public Sector Mainstreaming
2. Decentralisation
3. Private sector contributions
4. Airtime Tax
5. Flight tax
6. Social health insurance
7. New borrowing
8. Improving efficiencies in HIV/AIDS programmes to reduce resource needs

This section focuses on Options 1 to 7. Option 8 is considered in Section 7.

5.1 Public Sector Mainstreaming

Mainstreaming, as defined by UNAIDS is “essentially a process whereby a sector analyses how HIV and AIDS can impact it now and in the future, and considers how sectoral policies, decisions and actions might influence the longer-term development of the epidemic and the sector”. It is not about imposing HIV activities where they are inappropriate but is instead of ensuring that those who understand the sector take responsibility for contributing to the national AIDS response (UNAIDS, 2005).

The process of mainstreaming HIV/AIDS into a sector involves first analysing how HIV/AIDS impacts on the sector now and in the future, both internally and externally and then determining how the sector should respond based on its comparative advantage. Mainstreamed actions can be in the form of policies or practices that reduce vulnerability of staff or support those staff living with or impacted by HIV/AIDS – this is known as “internal mainstreaming”. Alternatively, mainstreamed actions could mean that prevention, treatment and support activities are incorporated into sectoral programmes – this is known as “external mainstreaming”. In the education sector for example, internal mainstreaming might mean that support and care is offered to HIV positive teachers whereas external mainstreaming could be in the form of behavioural change and communication (BCC) for pupils.

One tangible means of public sector mainstreaming is to make it compulsory for each ministry to allocate a budget for HIV/AIDS activities both in the workplace and as part of its operations. It is this kind of policy that we explore in this section.

5.1.1 International Experience

Most countries with generalised AIDS epidemics have multisectoral AIDS policy in place. Multisectorality, by definition, implies mainstreaming: all agencies covered by the policy, public as well as private, engage in addressing the epidemic. International practice with mainstreaming in this sense is therefore widespread, and also in place in Burkina Faso (see more below).

Some countries, such as Swaziland and Lesotho, have gone further and established a regulatory framework which seeks to ensure that public agencies effectively contribute a fixed percentage of their 'budget allocation' to HIV and AIDS.

In Swaziland the Government has issued a decree which recommends that public bodies devote 2% of their budget to workplace policies for their staff. The Public Sector HIV and AIDS Coordination Committee (PSHACC), which regroups the under-secretaries of the public bodies concerned, oversees the policy. Only recently a Secretariat and a Public Sector HIV and AIDS Workplace Policy have been instated which is expected to give impetus to this initiative. However, at present very few public bodies reportedly devote up to 2% of resources to workplace policy. With total public expenditure standing at US\$ 1.3 billion in 2008/09, 2% would amount to US\$ 26 million, which is about 30% of the total resources for AIDS in Swaziland in 2008/09.

In Lesotho the Government had a similar policy in place that recommended public bodies to spend up to 2% of their budgets internal mainstreaming i.e. through workplace policies for their staff. However, this policy has in effect been replaced by a yearly allocation from the Prime Minister's Office to the National AIDS Commission. If the recommendation would be followed through this policy initiative would yield significant resources for AIDS: with total recurrent expenditure by Ministries standing at US\$ 735 million in 2008/09, 2% would amount to US\$ 16 million, which is more than 25% of the total resources for AIDS in Lesotho in 2008/09.

The box below gives some further detail about experience with mainstreaming in the World Bank's MAP programme in Africa. It is indicative both of the potential of mainstreaming, but also of the operational difficulties involved in putting in place an effective mainstreaming policy.

Lessons learned from HIV/AIDS mainstreaming through the World Bank's Multi-Country AIDS Programme for Africa (MAP) (Word Bank, 2009)

- HIV/AIDS activities in many sector operations were not large enough to become a formal project component that can be monitored, and very few had been evaluated.
- In many countries, budget guidelines within sectors were not available to ensure mainstreaming of HIV/AIDS budgets.
- When activities were retrofitted into an ongoing project, there was often no documentation on the objectives, nor selection of HIV indicators, nor performance measurement at the project's close.
- With a few exceptions, project supervision resources were limited in providing HIV/AIDS expert assistance for the small specialized interventions in sectors that had little HIV/AIDS expertise.
- At the country level, almost all public sectors have part-time HIV/AIDS focal points, often supported by the MAP. These focal points lack capacity and knowledge in key areas including: (a) determining the impact of HIV on the sector; (b) strategic planning and fund mobilization; (c) action planning; (d) monitoring and evaluation of sector activities. One critical bottleneck is the availability of funds to undertake analytical work to influence substantial response to HIV/AIDS.
- Monitoring and Evaluation of sector-led activities is very weak. Only Education and Transport sectors have done impact evaluations and have a fairly good idea of how to address HIV/AIDS in their operations in the medium- to long-term.
- HIV/AIDS responses must be tailored to local and diverse needs (considering the type of epidemic) if they are to be effective. No single approach fits all local epidemics. HIV/AIDS epidemics vary from country to country or even within the same country. The drivers of the respective local epidemics need to be identified and HIV/AIDS interventions customized to address them.

5.1.2 National practice

The HIV/AIDS response in Burkina Faso is based on a multisectoral approach and this is firmly rooted in the Strategic Framework for the fight against HIV, AIDS and STIs (2011 – 2015). The public sector is recognised as one of the key sectors in the response and this goes beyond the responsibilities of the ministry of health and the other ministries for which HIV/AIDS activities fall within their specialist area of operation. The Strategy for Accelerated Growth and Sustainable development - Stratégie de Croissance Accélérée et de Développement durable (SCAD) - which is soon to replace the PRSP - Cadre Strategique de Lutte Contre la Pauvreté (CSLP) – recognises that the fight against HIV/AIDS is not just the responsibility of the Ministry of Health but is a problem of national development that affects all sectors and has a negative impact on economic activity.

In Burkina Faso each line ministry, decentralised unit, government agency and public association is obliged to include a budget line for activities to combat HIV/AIDS, including prevention and treatment of staff members who are HIV positive. The size of this budget is for each ministry to determine and depends on the number of staff

members that are HIV positive (and who are aware of their status) and on the preventative work they plan to carry out. That is to say the amount budgeted and the types of activities covered vary considerably across ministries. In most cases, ministries do not carry out the activities themselves but in the case of treatment, they reimburse staff for treatment received or in the case of prevention, they contract private companies or NGOs to carry out sensitisation activities.

Table 5.1 below gives an idea of the amount of money spent on HIV/AIDS by selected ministries in 2008. It shows that the vast majority of public health funding is channelled through the SP-CNLS (78%) followed by the ministry of health at central (11%) and regional level (8%). Other than these, only the Ministry of Social Development which accounts for about 2% of public sector spending on HIV/AIDS, allocated significant amounts to this area. In fact, the spending of all other ministries put together amounts to less than 1% of public sector spending on HIV/AIDS.

Table 5.1 Share of AIDS expenditure by public financing agency, 2008

	Total (FCFA)	Total (USD)	%
Ministry of Health (or equivalent sector entity)	1,860,639,677	3,917,136	10.98
Ministry of Education (or equivalent sector entity)	39,250,305	82,632	0.23
Ministry of Social Development (or equivalent sector entity)	351,610,750	740,233	2.07
Ministry of Defense (or equivalent sector entity)	6,800,000	14,316	0.04
Ministry of Finance (or equivalent sector entity)	15,000,000	31,579	0.09
Ministry of Labour (or equivalent sector entity)	1,000,000	2,105	0.01
Other Ministries	98,255,721	206,854	0.58
National Coordination Body (SP-CNLS)	13,248,368,049	27,891,301	78.18
Ministry of Health - provincial / regional level Health (or equivalent sector entity)	1,325,573,573	2,790,681	7.82
Total Public Financing	16,946,498,075	35,676,837	100.00

Source: NASA 2008

Looking at expenditure on HIV/AIDS as a proportion of total expenditure by ministry, Table 5.2 shows that other than the Ministry of Health, SP-CNLS and the Ministry of Social Action and National Solidarity no other ministry channelled as much as 0.5% of its expenditure on HIV/AIDS. In fact the highest proportion spent was by the Ministry of Employment, Labour and Social Security for which 0.1% of expenditure went on HIV/AIDS.

Table 5.2 Proportion of total executed funds spent on HIV/AIDS by Public agency in 2008, million Francs CFA

Ministry or Institution	Total Execution of Ministries (2008)	Total Expenditure on HIV/AIDS (2008)	% of expenditure By public agency on HIV/AIDS
Ministry of Health	57,618.07	1,860.64	3.23%
Ministry of Literacy and Basic Education	81,929.28	-	-
Ministry of Secondary and Higher Level Education and Scientific Research	44,345.27	-	-
Total Education Sector	126,274.55	39.25	0.03%
Ministry of Social Action and National Solidarity	5,907.96	351.61	5.95%
Ministry of Defense	56,427.22	6.80	0.01%
Ministry of Finance and the Economy	23,238.32	15.00	0.06%
Ministry of Employment, Labour and Social Security	911.80	1.00	0.11%
All other ministries	178,692.62	98.26	0.05%
SP-CNLS	13,248.37	13,248.37	100%
Municipality Expenditure*	140,704.88	1,325.57	0.94%

Source: NASA 2008 and Government of Burkina Faso Budget and Execution Data

* This is the inter-ministerial total i.e. not just spending on health

** Figures taken from NASA. All expenditure assumed to be accounted for here

Current allocations to HIV/AIDS by public agencies other than the Ministry of Health and the Social Action and National Solidarity are small in relation to their budget. However, at the same time the principle of 'mainstreaming' is firmly embedded in the main policy documents, such as the SCAD and the Strategic Framework for the fight against HIV, AIDS and STIs (2011 – 2015). This opens a clear perspective to expand this initiative. In the sections below we explore how much resources an enhanced mainstreaming initiative could generate in Burkina Faso.

5.1.3 Estimate of additional resources

5.1.3.1 Internal Mainstreaming

The key variables which would ideally be used in the calculation of future allocation of internal mainstreaming would include: the size of the workforce, the HIV prevalence among staff (if deemed to be different from the national prevalence), the size of the ministry and the overall financial and human resource capacity of the ministry. While we do not have information on each of these factors, we can use the wage bill as an, albeit crude, proxy of the size of the workforce in each ministry.

Taking figures from 2009, there are 12 ministries which together account for 94% of the total wage bill (see Table 5.3). Although salaries cannot directly imply the number of workers since salaries vary depending on the skill set of the workers, Table 5.3 shows that the wage bill does appear to increase in line with staff numbers and is highest for the ministries with the highest number of staff such as the Ministry of Literacy and Basic Education and the Ministry of Defence.

Table 5.3 Total salaries paid by ministry in Burkina Faso in 2009, million Francs CFA

Ministry	Salaries Paid by Ministry 2009	% of the total wage bill accounted for by each ministry
Ministry of Territorial Administration and Decentralization	3,247	1.4%
Ministry of Justice and the Promotion of Human Rights	3,374	1.5%
Ministry of Defense	44,254	19.4%
Ministry of Foreign Affairs	9,027	4.0%
Ministry of Security	10,261	4.5%
Ministry of Finance and the Economy	10,403	4.6%
Ministry of Health	24,227	10.6%
Ministry of Social Action and National Solidarity	2,847	1.2%
Ministry of Literacy and Basic Education	66,130	28.9%
Ministry of Secondary and Higher Level Education and Scientific Research	18,757	8.2%
Ministry of Agriculture	5,120	2.2%
Interministerial municipalities	16,597	7.3%
Other ministries	14,193	6.2%
Total	228,436	100%

Source: Burkina Faso Dotation et Exécution (1994 – 2009)

5.1.3.2 External Mainstreaming

The allocation of funding for external mainstreaming depends on the type of work undertaken by the ministry, with some ministries having more scope for incorporating HIV/AIDS activities into their sectoral operations than others. Table 5.4 shows the budget allocations for eight ministries who have scope for external mainstreaming activities (note that the Ministry of Health is not included here as it is assumed to be already addressing the needs of its target population). If each of these ministries were to allocate 1% of their 2009 budget to mainstreaming activities, this would mean a significant increase in public spending on HIV within these sectors – this is shown in Table 5.5.

Table 5.4 Total Budget allocation for selected ministries with scope for external mainstreaming

Ministry	Budget in millions of Francs CFA				
	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Ministry of Defense	37,443	43,860	53,879	58,484	62,222
Ministry of Employment, Labour and Social Security	1,520	1,981	511	750	871
Ministry of the Promotion of Women	317	336	635	800	633
Ministry of Social Action and National Solidarity	3,275	4,455	5,006	5,718	5,331
Ministry of Literacy and Basic Education	48,888	69,113	64,745	80,946	88,727
Ministry of Secondary and Higher Level Education and Scientific Research	31,267	36,960	38,967	42,786	51,585
Ministry of Agriculture	13,555	21,574	19,693	27,000	28,263
Ministry of Transport and Tourism	0	0	2,139	1,131	3,107

Table 5.5 presents a possible estimated amount of funds for internal and external mainstreaming for one year. Internal mainstreaming is calculated as 1% of the wage bill for all ministries whereas external mainstream is calculated as 1% of the total allocated budget for selected ministries with relevant lines of work.

Table 5.5 Projected Annual Amounts for Internal and External Mainstreaming

Ministry or Institution	Total Expenditure on HIV/AIDS (2008) Millions of F CFA	Projected Internal Mainstreaming (1% of wage bill)	Projected External Mainstreaming (1% of 2009 Budget)
Ministry of Health	1,860	242	
Ministry of Literacy and Basic Education	-	661	887
Ministry of Secondary and Higher Level Education and Scientific Research	-	187	515
Total Education Sector	39		
Ministry of Social Action and National Solidarity	351	28	53
Ministry of Defense	6	442	622
Ministry of Finance and the Economy	15	104	
Ministry of Justice and the Promotion of Human Rights	-	33	
Ministry of Employment, Labour and Social Security	1		8
Ministry of the promotion of women	-		6
Ministry of Agriculture	-	51	282
Ministry of Transport and Tourism			31
All other ministries	98	367	
SP-CNLS	13,248		
Municipality Expenditure*	1,325	165	
Total	16,946	2,284	2,407

A policy of internal mainstreaming where 1% of the wage bill is devoted to HIV/AIDS would generate an additional FCA 2,285 million (US\$ 4.7 million). If ministries devote 1% of their budget allocation to external mainstreaming this would yield another FCA 2,407 million (US\$ 4.9 million). Taken together a full fledged mainstreaming policy would generate FCA 4,692 million (US\$ 9.7 million), which corresponds with an additional 27% of the public resources currently devoted to HIV/AIDS.

5.1.4 Projection

The putting in place of an exhaustive public sector internal and external mainstreaming policy will require time. First, a consensus in Parliament has to be found and translated into a regulatory framework. We suggest that this would take 1 year and therefore implementation would commence in 2012. Second, to optimise efficiency and effectiveness of the programme, we suggest to phase in the programme over a period of three years from 2012 to 2014. Thereafter, the resources mobilised through this

mechanism will be dependent on the growth of total public sector wage bill and expenditure.⁴

Table 5.6 Projected Resources for Internal and External Mainstreaming, 2011 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Internal mainstreaming	-	0.9	2.0	3.2	3.4	3.7	4.0	4.3	4.6	5.0
External mainstreaming	-	0.9	2.1	3.4	3.6	3.9	4.2	4.5	4.9	5.3

5.2 Decentralisation

Contributions for HIV/AIDS by decentralised authorities is grounded in a rationale very similar to public sector mainstreaming: local authorities are well placed to understand the needs of the population, have an explicit mandate to address those needs and should be able to improve the effectiveness of public spending.

Local authorities often have some aspects of health service delivery within their mandate, as well as resource allocation decision power for specified categories of expenditure. This then indicates that local authorities will mobilise resources for HIV/AIDS inasmuch as it is a need within the population they administer and they have discretionary power to allocate resources to the services required.

The process of decentralisation in Burkina Faso started in 1995 and in 2006 about 18,000 municipal and regional councillors were elected in the first national election. However, many challenges remain, the most important of which insufficient capacity of local authorities and, partly as a result thereof, a piecemeal implementation of the decentralisation project, with as a result that in many areas spending and service delivery is still centrally determined (World Bank, 2009).

With the laws 055-2004 (about the decentralised administrative units (“collectivités territoriales”) and 014-2006 (about revenue and expenditure of decentralised administrative units) the decentralisation project has a solid legal footing. Decentralised agencies have a mandate to operate in the area of HIV/AIDS, with art 21 of Law 014-2006 allowing for discretionary spending as long as it pursues a ‘local interest’. Similarly, art 9 of the law 055-2004 indicates that local territorial entities can undertake any activity to promote economic, social and cultural development and articles 93 and 94 transfer competencies to do with addressing health problems. These articles seem to provide a strong legal basis for decentralised administrative units to engage resources in the area of HIV and AIDS.

Decentralised administrative unites collected roughly USD40 million in both 2007 and 2008. Most of these were locally raised except for a grant received to support their functioning, which we exclude from local revenue.

⁴ In the macroeconomic framework, this is achieved by fixing the share of discretionary current expenditure (i.e. current expenditure less interest costs and ear-marked funds) attributed to these two funding streams.

Table 5.7 Revenue of decentralised administrative units 2007 and 2008

<i>CFA Billion</i>	2007	2008
Revenue - recurrent	19,396,680,273	19,092,326,010
Of which: dotations	1,039,297,132	274,674,300
Of which: subventions	4,157,600	18,489,889
Total locally raised recurrent revenue	18,353,225,541	18,799,161,821

We predicted local revenue by assuming that the average ratio over the years 2007 and 2008 of the 'total revenue decentralised administrative units / Central Government tax revenue' remains constant over the period 2010-2020.

Key informants in Burkina Faso suggested that the decentralised administrative units struggle financially. That is why we suggest that decentralised units spend 1% of their revenue for recurrent spending (except for higher level grants) towards HIV and AIDS in the period 2012 to 2020. The results are evidently modest, and shown in the table below. They range from USD700,000 to USD1,250,000 in 2020.

Table 5.8 Projected Resources for Decentralisation, 2011 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Decentralisation	0	0	0.32	0.37	0.40	0.43	0.46	0.50	0.54	0.58

5.3 Private sector contributions

HIV/AIDS mainstreaming in the private sector is the process whereby private sector actors "address the causes and effects of AIDS in an effective and sustained manner, both through their usual work and within their workplace" (UNAIDS, 2005). The trend towards private sector mainstreaming can be motivated by a sense of corporate citizenship or by the direct effect that HIV/AIDS has or could have on their business including:

Increased costs such as health insurance, sick leave, funeral benefits as well as recruitment and training of new staff

Reduced productivity caused by increased absenteeism (due to illness, attending funerals or caring for the sick), high staff turnover, loss of intellectual capital and loss of morale.

Weakened business environment due to the strain on the economy and the fall in investment

Fall in the demand for goods and services as household disposable income falls due to higher health care costs or loss of income

Private companies and businesses have a unique role to play in the fight against HIV/AIDS both because of their interaction with the age group that are disproportionately affected by the virus and because structures, communications systems and training capacities that are already in place can be used for prevention, care and support programmes. Workplace programmes are increasingly recognised as effective, cost-efficient and sustainable approach to combating HIV/AIDS.

In addition to workplace programmes, some companies go further than their own workplace and advocate for increased engagement in HIV/AIDS work by other companies, sectors, communities, consumer groups and governments.

5.3.1 International practice

In a number of high prevalence countries, business coalitions have been formed with the objective of strengthening the private sector response to the epidemic. Below are some examples of HIV/AIDS coalitions that have proved to be effective in ensuring a more coordinated and effective response in the countries where they are active.

The HIV/AIDS business coalition in Rwanda, “Association du privé et para-étatique dans la lutte contre le VIH/SIDA” (APELAS), was created in 2001 and at that time was funded almost entirely through the World Bank’s Multi-country AIDS Programme (MAP). Currently the most active members are large parastatal companies such as Rwandex and private companies such as Gassecc and Intersec, (both security companies) whose employees represent high risk groups. Some of the core activities carried out by APELAS include: Sensitisation campaigns and prevention activities such as the distribution of condoms in companies; the provision of technical assistance to its members to support the elaboration of HIV/AIDS action plans; training for counselors and focal points; and advocacy to donors.

The Coalition of Enterprises against HIV/AIDS in the Ivory Coast (CECI) was established to promote integrated and effective programmes to fight against HIV, TB and Malaria among companies in the Ivory Coast. These objectives are realised through the exchange of best practice; the strengthening of prevention and treatment and the promotion of public private partnerships. Some of the specific activities undertaken include the provision of technical assistance; training; advocacy and resource mobilisation and monitoring and evaluation support.

The Zambia Business Coalition (ZBCA) was established to mobilise the private sector response to HIV/AIDS. It supports firms to mitigate against the negative impact of HIV amongst staff members; promotes prevention campaigns and facilitates coordination between businesses and technical services and the community. It also provides training for HIV/AIDS focal points within companies.

5.3.2 National practice

In Burkina Faso the multisectoral and decentralised approach adopted in 1998 emphasises the importance of involving all actors and socioeconomic sectors in the national response to HIV/AIDS. The Strategic Framework for the fight against HIV, AIDS and STIs (2011 – 2015) sets out the institutional framework by which this operates, and as part of this it specifies four key groups: the public sector, the private sector and enterprises, the community and the national coordination sector. The group “private

sector and enterprises” includes all public, parastatal and private businesses and the informal sector.

According to the Order N°2002/PRES/CNLS-ITS/SP of June 2002, industrial and commercial enterprises with fifty or more employees should set up a *Company Committee for the fight against HIV, AIDS and STIs* (CELS) with a maximum of 8 members headed by a coordinator. The purpose of these committees are to plan and coordinate activities in the fight against HIV/AIDS and STIs; advocate for additional resources; mobilise and manage resources available; engage with company officials in the fight against HIV, AIDS and STIs; elaborate action plans and submit them to SP-CNLS and support the monitoring and evaluation of the approved action plan.

Since 2005, the ILO has supported the *Education Programme on HIV/AIDS in the Workplace*. As of January 2010, 27 companies were supported by the programme each of which have appointed a focal point and have established a joint committee on the fight against HIV/AIDS. As part of this programme, all of these organizations have established: a programme on the education of HIV/AIDS; a condom distribution service; an information service on STIs; a VCT service and a prevention and treatment service. The project also operates at the national level through capacity building of government officials and employers and through the support of the sectoral plan for the fight against HIV/AIDS in the workplace.

A National Coalition of the Private Sector and Businesses in the fight against HIV/AIDS (CNSPE) was established in 2008 to boost the response of the sector through improved coordination and synergy thereby leading to greater efficiency and effectiveness. As per the operational manual, the function of the Coalition is to (i) coordinate the activities of the sector including coordinating and guiding the work of the CELS (ii) mobilise funds (iii) provide technical support (iv) improve and strengthen the support for workers infected with HIV/AIDS (v) monitoring and evaluation of activities taking into account the diversity of the sector. Despite the progress that has been made, movement to fully operationalise the coalition has been slow. Some of the reasons for this are: inadequacy and uncertainty of funding; insufficient engagement of key actors; lack of clarity in the functional linkages between parties and the challenges relating to organising the informal sector.

5.3.3 Estimate of additional resources

Table 5.99 shows the projected resource needs required to provide workplace programmes for those employed in industry and services and those in waged employment in agriculture during the period 2008 to 2015. These figures were calculated by the SP-CNLS and are based on the following unit costs:

- \$5.45 for peer education per pair of employees
- \$6.33 for STIs treated in the work-place
- \$0.33 per male condom distributed

The calculations are also based on assumptions about the proportion of the labour force working in industry and services and in waged employment in agriculture and on the progressive increase in provision of workplace programmes over the coming years.

Table 5.9 Projected resource needs for Workplace Programmes (peer education, STI treatment and condom distribution) for the period 2008 to 2015

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Population size								
Male population 15 – 64	3301262	3400050	3504647	3616732	3736493	3863955	4000984	4148615
Female population 15-64	3915215	4051782	4191034	4335817	4486040	4641434	4805256	4978402
Number of employees in formal employment	1,548,641	1,598,512	1,650,344	1,705,078	1,762,748	1,823,310	1,887,829	1,956,731
Coverage								
% of the LF provided with peer education (in pairs)	0%	1%	2%	2%	3%	4%	4%	5%
% of the LF receiving treatment for STIs	1%	2%	3%	5%	6%	7%	9%	10%
% of the LF provided with condoms	0%	1%	2%	2%	3%	4%	4%	5%
Results								
Workers provided with peer education (in pairs)	3,778	14,485	25,883	38,032	50,991	64,816	79,610	95,473
Cases of STIs treated	147	557	982	1,424	1,884	2,360	2,856	3,375
Condoms provided (in millions)	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
Resources required (US \$)	38,564	163,567	299,666	453,205	625,387	818,155	1,034,232	1,276,530

According to information obtained from the Chamber of Commerce, there are currently over forty three thousand private companies in Burkina Faso (see Table 5.105.10). Just under two hundred of these have more than fifty employees, each of which are obliged, by government order, to set up a company committee or *CELS*.

Table 5.10 The number of private companies in Burkina Faso by industry and number of employees.

Number of staff, by group	Category				Total
	Artisanal	Business	Industry	Services	
[1 - 4]	1,847.0	22,765.0	4,883.0	11,323.0	40,818.0
[5 - 9]	44.0	508.0	625.0	423.0	1,600.0
[10 – 24]	14.0	200.0	183.0	258.0	655.0
[25 – 49]	3.0	57.0	52.0	76.0	188.0
[50 – 99]	1.0	22.0	42.0	38.0	103.0
[100 +]	1.0	15.0	48.0	29.0	93.0
Total	1,910.0	23,567.0	5,833.0	12,147.0	43,457.0

Source: Chamber of Commerce

Another useful source of information on the private sector in Burkina Faso is the *Directoire Générale des Impôts*. Here we obtained information on 100 of the largest private companies in Burkina Faso in 2009. Table 5.115.11 classifies these companies as in the previous table, by number of employees and calculates the total annual cost of providing workplace programmes in these 100 firms as \$25,817. These figures are based on the unit costs used by the SP-CNLS and assumes the following:

- Peer education is costed by pair of employee.
- One male condom is distributed per employee.
- The number of people treated for STIs is based on the incidence rate in 2008 – 0.9% for men and 3.5% for women. It also assumes that 70% of the staff members in these companies are male.

Table 5.11 shows an estimate of the average cost across each category of company which ranges from \$9 in the case of companies with between 1 and 4 employees and \$904 for those with more than 100 employees. Since these amounts are not high relative to the size of the company, it should be possible for all companies to carry out these three activities in the short term.

Table 5.11 Estimated Cost of Peer Education, STI Treatment and Condom Distribution across the 100 largest companies in Burkina Faso, 2009.

Category of Companies	Number of Companies	Total Number of Employees per category	Cost of peer education	Cost of Male Condom Distribution (one per worker) US\$	Cost of Treating STIs US\$	Total Cost per Category of Company US\$	Average Cost per Company in Each Category US\$
[1 - 4]	6	15	41	13	2	56	9
[5 - 9]	12	77	210	69	8	287	24
[10 - 24]	32	573	1,561	515	60	2,137	67
[25 - 49]	17	609	1,660	548	64	2,271	134
[50 - 99]	13	801	2,183	720	84	2,987	230
[100 +]	20	4,847	13,208	4,359	511	18,078	904
Total	100	6,922	18,863	6,225	730	25,817	258

Source: *Directoire Générale des Impôts* (DGI)

Combining information from the two previous tables and making a cautious assumption about the number of employees per company, Table 5.12 presents an estimation of the cost of carrying out workplace programmes in all companies in Burkina Faso. According to these calculations if all private companies were to carry out peer education programmes, distribute condoms and provide STI treatment as per the assumptions detailed above, the total annual amount spent by the private sector on HIV/AIDS workplace programmes would be about US\$345,598.

Table 5.12 Estimated Cost of Workplace Programmes for a all companies in Burkina Faso, 2009

Category of company by no. of employees	Total no. of Companies	Estimated no. of workers per company	Estimated total no. of workers	Estimated no. of peer education programmes	Estimated no. of workers needing STI treatment	Estimated cost of peer education programmes	Estimated cost of STI treatment (US\$)	Estimated cost of male condom distribution	Total estimated Cost
[1 - 4]	40,818	2	61,227	30,614	1,020	166,845	6,454	20,205	193,504
[5 - 9]	1,600	7	11,200	5,600	186	30,520	1,181	3,696	35,397
[10 - 24]	655	17	11,135	5,568	185	30,343	1,174	3,675	35,191
[25 - 49]	188	37	6,956	3,478	116	18,955	733	2,295	21,984
[50 - 99]	103	75	7,674	3,837	128	20,910	809	2,532	24,252
[100 +]	93	120	11,160	5,580	186	30,411	1,176	3,683	35,270
Total	43,457		109,352	54,676	1,821	297,986	11,526	36,086	345,598

Enterprises with less than 9 employees potentially generate two-thirds of resources through this mechanism. At the same time it is difficult to police these small entities, and costs of monitoring and enforcement will quickly be higher than their potential contribution to HIV/AIDS. Bigger companies, i.e. with more than 9 employees could generate US\$ 116,697, through contributions for peer education programmes, STI treatment for their employees and condom distribution. While the operational aspects of such a scheme need to be explored further, it is assumed that these enterprises would 'purchase' these services from a third party provider, instead of organising themselves. Monitoring whether these companies comply to this policy is easier and can go hand in hand with existing information and monitoring requirements.

5.3.4 Projection

We assume that only companies with more than 9 employees would be required to participate in this scheme. We assume that it will take one year to put in place the regulatory framework for the scheme. The start date would therefore be 2012. Thereafter, the value of the resources raised by the scheme is expected to grow in line with GDP.

Table 5.13 Projected Resources for Private Sector Workplace Schemes, 2011 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Workplace schemes	-	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1

5.4 Airtime Tax

In a small number countries, Gabon for example, the government has or is about to introduce a levy on mobile phone airtime as one means of overcoming the national

HIV/AIDS financing gap. This levy has been faced with criticism primarily due to the distortionary effects on the mobile phone industry and the disproportionate burden that it places on the poor who increasingly rely on mobile phone coverage as a means of communication.

While there are very few examples of countries who have implemented this kind of tax for the purpose of raising funds for HIV/AIDS, there are a number of African countries who impose a specific levy on mobile phones that are not earmarked for a particular type of expenditure. In East African Community Countries for example, these tax rates are particularly high ranging between 5% and 12% and are increasing despite strong opposition from mobile phone operators who are struggling to increase market penetration as well as the volume of minutes sold. In Uganda, the airtime tax increased progressively from 5% in 2002 to 10% in 2004⁵ while in Rwanda, excise tax on mobile phones was increased from 5% to 8% in the 2010 budget. A recent report entitled "Taxation and the Growth of Mobile Services in Sub-Saharan Africa" produced by GSMA claims that such taxes are regressive in nature as they penalise the poorer sections of society. It also claims that by lowering taxes on mobile phones, governments will in fact increase receipts as millions more people will be able to afford to use mobile phones.

5.4.1 International practice

In Kenya, the NACC have proposed a 2% levy on every mobile phone voice minute sold in addition to the excise tax of 10% currently in place. If this is endorsed by the cabinet, the NACC hopes to raise about Sh11 billion (US\$ 135 million) for the purchase of ARVs over five years.

5.4.2 National practice

Currently there is no specific levy on mobile phones in Burkina Faso. Value Added Tax, which is governed by article 318 to 386 of the Tax Code, is applied on all transactions at a uniform rate of 18%. Corporation tax which is applied to industrial, commercial and agricultural corporations is levied on net profits at the rate of 30%.

There are three main mobile phone operators in Burkina: Telmob, Telcel and Zain (to become Bharti Airtel as of October 2010). Telemob is the market leader with about 45% of the market share⁶. Table 5.14 indicates the latest available data on annual turnover for the three main operators in Burkina Faso.

According to a report published in January 2010, mobile phone market penetration in Burkina Faso is extremely low which means that the next few years may see an expansion of mobile phone coverage in the country (Budde, 2010).

⁵ www.balancingact-africa.com Issue no. 291, 5th February 2006

⁶ <http://www.sage.fr/mge/temoignages/logiciels-finances/comptabilite/telmob-sage-1000-comptabilite-immobilisations>

Table 5.14 Turnover of Mobile Phone Operators in Burkina Faso

Operator	Year	Turnover (FCFA)
TELMOB	2009	66,499,955,097
CELTEL BURKINA (ZAIN)	2008	54,438,542,662
TELECEL FASO (MOOV)	2008	21,480,771,733

5.4.3 Estimate of additional resources

Ideally calculations of the expected revenue from this levy should be based on minutes of airtime sold. But since this data is not available, we base our estimations on the expected annual turnover as per Table 5.145.15.

We also need to make an assumption about the expansion of the mobile phone market in Burkina Faso in the coming years. Given the current low market penetration, we can assume quite a significant expansion in the next few years, though this expansion will slow considerably once the penetration rate is at higher levels.

We use figures from one of the operators, Telmob, to predict future turnover (see Table 5.155.14). These figures show a year on year increase in turnover of about 26%. Since Telemob is the biggest operator it is likely to have experienced higher growth rates than the other two operators. Furthermore, as already mentioned, it is unlikely that the industry will sustain such high growth rates.

Table 5.15 Turnover and Penetration Rate for Telemob 2005 to 2009

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009
Turnover	25.7	32.5	39.8		66.4
Penetration rate	4.99%	7.50%	11.70%		

Source: <http://www.telmob.bf/telmobsa/chiffrescles.htm>

In order to move from these rather summary data to an estimate of possible resource mobilisation for HIV/AIDS we have to make a number of further assumptions. First, we assume that only half of total turnover by mobile phone operators is from airtime. This is probably an underestimate. Second, we envisage the application of an additional 5% airtime tax, which is the lower limit of what is currently applied in some countries in Eastern Africa (see above). We take the lower limit because heavily taxing airtime faces increasing criticism.

Based on these assumptions an airtime levy of 5% could've generated an additional FCFA 3.2 billion in 2008 (US\$ 6.6 million).

5.4.4 Projection

We estimate the penetration of the mobile phone market in Burkina Faso to be S-shaped⁷, allowing for an expected acceleration in the near future, with subsequent decreasing growth rates.

Figure 5.1 Mobile phone market penetration 2008 - 2028

Using the 2008 figures, we see that the total penetration rate in the market was 31% and the total turnover of all operators was FCFA 129 billion. This implies a total market value of FCFA 4.17 billion for each percentage point of market penetration. We can use this ratio to extrapolate the market value, and hence the airtime tax, at each level of market penetration shown in Figure 6.1 above.

However, a further assumption must be made to allow for inflation over the time period. In addition, it is assumed that such a tax would not be in place until 2012. Combining these methods, we get the following projections.

Table 5.16 Projected Resources for a 5% airtime levy, 2011 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Total turnover	166.2	179.9	198.2	222.1	252.6	289.1	329.4	369.8	406.0
Airtime sold	83.1	90.0	99.1	111.1	126.3	144.5	164.7	184.9	203.0
Airtime tax of 5%	4.2	4.5	5.0	5.6	6.3	7.2	8.2	9.2	10.2

⁷ We use a logistic function $P(t) = [K \cdot P(0) \cdot \exp(rt)] / [K + (P(0) \cdot \exp(rt) - 1)]$, with $P(t)$ the penetration rate at time t , K the carrying capacity and r the growth rate.

5.5 Flight tax

Revenue generated through the collection of a tax on flight departures represents a new opportunity to raise money for HIV/AIDS. Some of the arguments in favour of implementing a tax on flights instead of other forms of direct or indirect taxes are outlined briefly here:

Progressivity: In both developed and developing countries, air passengers do not usually form part of the poorest segments of the population. A tax charged on flight purchased are therefore progressive, particularly if a higher amount is payable for business class and first class tickets. The progressivity of the tax may also be enhanced by charging a zero rate on domestic flights or by charging a higher levy for first or business class passengers.

Economic neutrality: As with the design of any new tax, a major concern of national governments is the distortionary effects of increasing the cost of a product or service. Given that the price elasticity of demand for airline tickets is reasonably small however, the tax on flights should be economically neutral – ie it should not reduce the demand for flights, as long as the amount charged is small compared to the cost of the ticket. By the same token, the tax should not affect competition among airline carriers as all passengers travelling on the same route would be charged the same amount. To ensure that the tax is non-distortionary transit passengers should be exempt from the tax. This is based on the assumption that a tax on transit passengers might encourage them to change their route or fly with another airline – though this effect is likely to be negligible if the amount of the levy is very small relative to the cost of the ticket.

Easy to apply: In practical terms, the tax can simply be charged on purchase of ticket. Evidence from countries already administering this kind of levy indicates that the additional costs involved are minimal⁸.

5.5.1 International experience

A number of countries have implemented a flight tax with revenues targeted at the purchase of drugs for Malaria, TB and HIV/AIDS through the UNITAID⁹ initiative. These include France, Britain, Brazil, Chile, Côte d'Ivoire, Congo, Republic of Korea, Madagascar, Mauritius and Niger with several others already promising to come on board. The tax charged varies per country depending on whether the flight is domestic or international and whether the passengers are travelling in economy or business class. In France for example, the amount charged for domestic and European flights ranges from €1 for economy to €10 for business while for inter-continental flights the amount ranges from €4 to €40 for economy and business class respectively¹⁰. In Chile, a uniform tax of \$2 is payable by all passengers travelling on international flights from the capital city, Santiago.

⁸ Breton, Thierry (2005) Pilot project of a solidarity contribution on plane tickets. High Level Dialogue on Financing for Development (New York, June, 27 2005)

⁹ www.unitaid.eu

¹⁰ www.globalpolicy.org November 30, 2005

UNITAID was established to provide additional funding to support existing efforts in the fight against HIV/AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis. The additional funding comes primarily from a solidarity contribution on airline tickets. Through implementing partners, UNITAID channels its funds to purchasing tests and medicines of assured quality and ensuring fast delivery to the patients who most need them - those in low- and middle-income countries. Launched in September 2006, UNITAID was founded by the governments of Brazil, Chile, France, Norway and the United Kingdom. Today it is supported by 29 countries and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

In Kenya, the National AIDS Control Council (NACC) submitted a cabinet paper in June 2010 proposing a levy of Sh190 (about US\$2) for every passenger booked on an outbound flight and Sh3.50 (about US\$ 0.037) for every tonne of goods being ferried aboard airliners. If this is endorsed by the government it will come into affect in January 2011 and is expected to raise Sh12 billion (US\$148 million) over 5 years.

5.5.2 National practice

There is currently no tax on flights in Burkina Faso for the purpose of funding the fight against HIV/AIDS, nor has there been any active movement to establish such a levy. While the revenue generating potential of this tax is constrained by the relatively low volume of air traffic in Burkina Faso (in comparison to Kenya for example) the low administrative costs of implementing it means that it is certainly worth exploring further as a possible financing source for HIV/AIDS.

5.5.3 Estimate of additional resources

Table 5.175.17 below provides details of the total number of passengers who have travelled to all destinations (domestic, regional or international) from Ouagadougou and Bobo-Dioulasso airports each year from 2005 to 2009. In terms of overall volume, the vast majority of passengers depart on Regional and International flights from Ouagadougou, with far fewer travelling on domestic flights from either airport.

Table 5.17 Number of passengers departing annually on International and Regional Flights from Burkina Faso between 2005 and 2009

Year	Ouagadougou Airport			Bobo-Dioulasso Airport		
	Domestic	Regional	International	Domestic	Regional	International
2005	1,557	68,484	60,900	2,028	1,757	629
2006	1,741	80,060	58,210	2,186	1,847	352
2007	2,198	95,055	58,087	2,601	1,523	189
2008	1,458	94,914	59,719	1,497	1,262	513
2009	1,317	109,778	62,543	1,434	1,146	486

Source: Agence pour la Sécurité de la Navigation Aérienne (ASECNA)

In order to estimate the potential revenue from taxes levied on flights, we must first estimate the number of passengers departing on each type of flight during the coming years. During the period from 2005 to 2009, for each year other than 2008, there has been an increase in the total volume of departing passengers, with a year on year average increase in passengers during this five year period of 6.8% (see Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2 Total number of Passengers Departing on Domestic, Regional and International Flights in Burkina Faso each Year from 2005 to 2009

Taking the geometric means across each type of flight, the trend in air passenger departures from 2005 to 2009 are as follows: an average fall of 6.4% per annum for domestic flights, an average increase of 12.1% per annum for regional flights and an average increase of 0.6% per annum for international flights. However, since the variation across years is so pronounced, especially in 2008, where the fall in domestic passengers for example was 38.4%, compared to an increase of 22% in 2007, it would not make sense to base the predictions of future volumes purely on these figures. If instead we assume that the number of domestic passengers increases by 2%, regional passengers increase by 8% and international passengers by 4% this would result in a similar overall pattern for the period 2011 to 2015 as was found in 2005 to 2009 with a year on year average increase overall of 6.6%. The estimated numbers of passengers based on these assumptions are presented in Table 5.185.18.

Table 5.18 Estimated volume of departing passengers on domestic, regional and international flights in Burkina Faso during the period 2011 to 2015

	Domestic	Regional	International	Total
2011	2,862	129,382	68,172	200,416
2012	2,919	139,732	70,899	213,551
2013	2,978	150,911	73,735	227,624
2014	3,037	162,984	76,684	242,705
2015	3,098	176,022	79,752	258,872
2016	3,160	190,104	82,942	276,206
2017	3,223	205,312	86,260	294,795
2018	3,288	221,737	89,710	314,735
2019	3,353	239,476	93,299	336,128
2020	3,420	258,634	97,031	359,085

Having estimated the number of passengers departing each year, what remains is to apply a levy to each category of flight. Table 5.195.19 presents three different scenarios each producing different levels of funding. Scenario 1, which applies a \$2 levy on each departing ticket, relates closely to the model due to be implemented in Kenya in 2011. As already mentioned however, the volume of passengers in Burkina Faso is far less than in Kenya which means that such a low levy may not be appropriate in this context. Based on our assumptions of volumes of passengers, a levy of \$2 per passenger would produce between \$400,000 and \$720,000 per year during 2011 to 2020. Even with very low administrative costs, this level of revenue may not justify the tax reform.

Modelling the levy more in line with what is implemented in developed countries, Scenario 2 and 3 show how substantially more funding can be generated through this financing mechanism. Both of these scenarios place a zero levy on domestic flights and much higher levy for both regional and international flights than was applied in scenario 1. Scenario 2, which places a \$20 levy on regional flights and a \$30 levy on international flights, would produce annual revenues of between about \$4.5 million and \$6 million or \$26 million overall for the period 2011 to 2015. Scenario 3 on the other hand which places an even higher levy of \$25 on regional flights and \$40 on international flights would provide revenues of between \$6 million and \$10.3 million, or \$79.6 million overall over the 10 year period.

Table 5.19 Projected revenues from flight taxes

	Domestic	Regional	International	Total
Scenario 1	\$2	\$2	\$2	
2011	5,724	258,764	136,344	400,832
2012	5,838	279,464	141,798	427,100
2013	5,956	301,822	147,470	455,248
2014	6,074	325,968	153,368	485,410
2015	6,196	352,044	159,504	517,744
2016	6,320	380,208	165,884	552,412
2017	6,446	410,624	172,520	589,590
2018	6,575	443,474	179,420	629,470
2019	6,707	478,952	186,597	672,256
2020	6,841	517,268	194,061	718,170
Total	62,677	3,748,588	1,636,966	5,448,231
Scenario 2	\$0	\$20	\$30	
2011	0	2,587,640	2,045,160	4,632,800
2012	0	2,794,640	2,126,970	4,921,610
2013	0	3,018,220	2,212,050	5,230,270
2014	0	3,259,680	2,300,520	5,560,200
2015	0	3,520,440	2,392,560	5,913,000
2016	0	3,802,075	2,488,262	6,290,338
2017	0	4,106,241	2,587,793	6,694,034
2018	0	4,434,741	2,691,305	7,126,045
2019	0	4,789,520	2,798,957	7,588,477
2020	0	5,172,681	2,910,915	8,083,596
Total	0	37,485,878	24,554,492	62,040,370
Scenario 3	\$0	\$25	\$40	
2011	0	3,234,550	2,726,880	5,961,430
2012	0	3,493,300	2,835,960	6,329,260
2013	0	3,772,775	2,949,400	6,722,175
2014	0	4,074,600	3,067,360	7,141,960
2015	0	4,400,550	3,190,080	7,590,630
2016	0	4,752,594	3,317,683	8,070,277
2017	0	5,132,802	3,450,391	8,583,192
2018	0	5,543,426	3,588,406	9,131,832
2019	0	5,986,900	3,731,942	9,718,842
2020	0	6,465,852	3,881,220	10,347,072
Total	0	46,857,348	32,739,322	79,596,670

5.5.4 Projection

The above calculations highlight that in order for this tax to be viable, the size of the levy per passenger would have to be significant, perhaps in the region of \$20 to \$40, depending on whether the flight is regional or international. The fact that these amounts represent a only a very small proportion of the price of the ticket and that these passengers are likely to be part of the wealthier segments of the population, mean that the tax should not affect their decision to travel (ie the price elasticity of demand is not high). Before making any conclusions about the desirability or appropriateness of implementing this type of tax, however, further work is required to investigate both the costs involved in collecting this tax as well as the political acceptability of such a levy.

The figures presented above assume a fixed fee (in US\$ terms) over the 10 year time horizon shown in the table. It could of course be possible to revise the fee upwards in line with inflation. However, in the remainder of this document we use the figures of scenario 2 (i.e. with a constant fee), though revenues are not assumed to flow until 2012.

Table 5.20 Projected Resources for Flight Tax, 2011 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Flight Tax	-	2.3	2.4	2.6	2.7	2.9	3.1	3.2	3.4	3.6

5.6 Social health insurance

Health insurance is a particularly attractive health financing modality. It converts out-of-pocket expenditure for health into pooled funding for health, thus increasing accessibility to health services and equity both in access and financing in the health system. Moreover, contemporary social health insurance regimes such as those in Rwanda and Ghana, seek to cover both the formal and informal sectors, and include contributions from employees as well as employers. If successful they can generate predictable and large flows of funds for health care, and by extension for HIV and AIDS.

5.6.1 International practice

Because of its attractive features as a health financing mechanism, the interest for social health insurance has remained high over time as an alternative, or complement, to tax based funded health care. Whereas progress has been challenging, countries like Ghana and Rwanda have achieved population coverage rates that were previously believed to be very difficult to achieve. Namibia and Kenya have explicitly looked into covering AIDS benefits in larger insurance pools.

In Namibia a risk equalisation fund, with donor subsidy, was established in 2006 which encouraged private not-for-profit insurers to diversify into the lower-income market and as such expand coverage. Under this product lower income individuals were able to buy an insurance plan for an annual premium of USD284 per person per year (2006 dollars) of which 19% was donor subsidised for the first three years of the fund's operation.

Simultaneously existing higher income individuals were offered to purchase HIV specific coverage for an additional USD35.52 (2006 dollars) which allows them to cover HIV drugs, laboratory tests and other treatment. The subsidy for poorer enrollees together with the contribution of existing richer members for specific AIDS benefits enabled the fund to enhance the resource pool considerably and cover HIV benefits.

Partly encouraged by the Namibian experience, the National AIDS Control Council in Kenya examined ways to deepen the population coverage rate of the National Hospital Insurance Fund (NHIF), and to include HIV and AIDS benefits into the benefit package. Currently the NHIF does not cover ARV or outpatient opportunistic infections treatment. A feasibility study however finds that an increase by 25% in NHIF premiums allows to cover outpatient first-line ARV and outpatient opportunistic infections, if the fund's population coverage ambitions, to cover 23% of the working population by 2015, are met. This proposal is currently seen as one of the major options to finance HIV and AIDS into the future in Kenya (Muchiri and Dutta 2010).

5.6.2 National practice

Burkina Faso has embarked on an ambitious project to set up a social health insurance system. At present only 7% of the workforce is covered by the public social security scheme, and the benefits do not include health care. There has been a strong development of community based health insurance schemes in Burkina, demonstrating the potential of health insurance in the country, but altogether covering only a small share of the population and with questions surrounding their financial viability.

The national scheme aims for universal coverage by incorporating both the current formal social security regime, as well as existing and future community based health insurance. The scheme would be mandatory for formal sector workers and voluntary for those active in the informal economy. Contributions from members are complemented by both domestic public as well as donor resources. Premiums would be differentiated over beneficiary groups, as well as, possibly, benefit packages, at least in the early stages of the scheme.

The project, although still in feasibility-study phase, benefits from high level political support. The project was approved in the Cabinet in August 2008 and a multi-stakeholder committee has been set up. A permanent secretariat is responsible to implement an agenda of studies and consultations (Gouvernement du Burkina Faso. Secretariat Permanent Assurance Maladie 2009).

In the remainder of this section we carry out an estimation of the increase in premium necessary to cover ARV need in the membership of the social health insurance in Burkina Faso at different points in time. We also estimate the resources mobilised for AIDS in this way. The hypotheses underlying the simulation are taken from documents and files, many of them work in progress, gratefully received from Mr Seinu Saibu and Mr Moussa Traore, from the Permanent Secretary – Health Insurance in Ouagadougou. They are working hypotheses and do not in any way reflect options taken at this stage. As the project is still very much in a conceptual phase we do not use these calculations in the resources availability estimate to cover the AIDS financing gap. But they do illustrate the potential of such a scheme for HIV/AIDS financing in Burkina Faso.

5.6.3 Estimate of additional resources

The main hypotheses used in the estimation, and subsequent extrapolation, come from working documents amongst which the SIMINS model used by the Permanent Secretary to simulate coverage and funding scenarios. Where necessary interpolations have been made. The hypotheses are:

- Average household size 5.3
- Dependency ratio: 0.81
- Target group shares in total population:
 - o Public sector: 2%
 - o Pensioners: 0.5%
 - o Private sector: 4.6%
 - o Informal sector: 92.9%
- Coverage expansion rate:

Coverage scenario SHI (%)	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Public sector	0	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Pensioners	0	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Private sector	0	50	<u>65</u>	80	<u>90</u>	100	100	100	100	100
Informal sector	0	5	<u>18</u>	30	<u>45</u>	60	<u>67</u>	<u>73</u>	80	<u>90</u>

Note: figures underlined are linear extrapolations

- It is assumed that 10% of the information sector population is exempt from paying fees. Sources to cover their premiums are to be found outside the Fund.
- Premium per member by sector per year (FCFA):

Public sector	9,674
Pensioners	3,114
Private sector	6,044
Informal sector	1,500

- Population in need of ARV and drug unit costs vary from year to year and are taken from resource needs estimate by NAC. The share of those in need of second line ARV is constant over the period at 2.7% of those in need of ART.
- The Fund's overhead is set at 15% for the first three years, 10% for the subsequent two years, and 7% thereafter.

Using these hypotheses we can compute the estimated number of covered members per year, those in need of ARV, and the cost associated to cover their ARV needs. We provide a summary of simulations in Annex B.

The cost to expand the 'standard health care benefit package' (currently not defined) would be between FCFA 287 and 405 per person per year in the period 2013 – 2020. As the premium for the 'standard package' varies over sub-groups, the share of the costs for AIDS in the total premium varies over sub-groups as well. This is shown in the graph below.

Table 5.21 Share of total premium to cover ARV costs by social health insurance sub-group in 2013

As the premium for informal sector workers is considerably lower than for public sector workers, the share of the premium to cover the ARV benefit is almost 20%. For public sector workers that is 4%. Even if the elasticity of demand for health insurance for the informal population is not known, a share edging towards 20% seems high. At the same time more than 90% of the population is in the informal sector. It is therefore important to better understand whether adding an ARV benefit to the standard health benefit package of informal sector workers would slow the uptake of what the voluntary insurance product. The population coverage projection, as currently projected by the working documents, is shown in the graph below.

Table 5.22 Social health insurance population coverage 2010-2020

The simulations also show that a social health insurance can be an important, sustainable and predictable, source of financing for AIDS. In the first year of operation, 2013, under the assumptions described above, the Fund would generate about USD 1 million to cover ARV costs. This grows to USD 8.6 million in 2020. When the entire population would be covered by the Fund, it could generate sufficient resources to cover all ARV needs. The major outstanding questions are:

- Whether the Fund will be able to cover the population as assumed;
- Whether the informal, and often poorer, population, will be willing to devote about 20% of the premium to cover ARV.

The validity of the simulations above very much hinge on the answers to these questions.

5.7 New borrowing

If the other sources of financing are not adequate, additional fiscal space can be created through additional borrowing. For political reasons, governments may also prefer to borrow rather than raise tax revenues. For the purposes of this analysis, we therefore model a modest increase in the size of the deficit in each year and assume that all of the additional expenditure is put towards HIV and AIDS.

Burkina Faso has received a significant amount of debt relief in the past under both the Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) Initiative and the Multilateral Debt Relief Initiative (MDRI). As a consequence, Burkina Faso's debt stock as a share of GDP was 28.2% at the end of 2010.

There are no universal rules that set a limit on how much debt a country can incur without facing repayment problems. A country must set its own debt strategy based on a wide range of country specific factors, such as the share of foreign denominated debt, the share of variable interest rate debt and the volatility of the country's economy, government revenues and exports. Nevertheless, there are two sources which can be used for comparison in this instance.

Firstly, the IMF/World Bank Debt Sustainability Framework proposes a limit for the Net Present Value (NPV) of external debt of 40% of GDP.¹¹ In Burkina Faso's case, the ratio of external debt stock to GDP was 24.9% at the end of 2010. Though debt stock and Net Present Value are not exactly the same, it is clear there may be room for additional borrowing based on this measure.

Secondly, the Growth and Stability Pact established a limit on the debt stock of 60% of GDP for the euro zone countries, though many of the member countries exceeded this ratio even before the financial crisis. As Burkina Faso's debt stock is 28% of GDP, this again suggests there may be room for additional borrowing.

However, there are a number of reasons why this option is not recommended. Firstly, there is a consequent impact on the debt stock and the risk of default. Despite the ratios mentioned above, Burkina Faso is classified as being at high risk of debt distress under the IMF-World Bank Debt Sustainability Framework due to its relatively high level of external debt and its vulnerability to a fall in exports.

Clearly, any additional borrowing to finance HIV expenditure, particularly borrowing from external sources, will exacerbate this situation. Even if the debt sustainability ratios remain within acceptable levels, there is a consequent increase in the risk of debt distress in the future.

Second, it is generally accepted that government borrowing should be used either for infrastructure projects (which can then "pay back" the investment in future years) or for temporary counter-cyclical fiscal policy. It should not be used to finance a permanent increase in current expenditure. It could be argued that spending on HIV and AIDS is an investment, in that it reduced future costs and improve growth, by increasing longevity and reducing infections, but at least part of the expenditures discussed here should be considered as current.

Thirdly, there can be negative macroeconomic consequences of increasing the government deficit. Depending on existing demand and supply, increasing the deficit can have inflationary consequences. Increasing government borrowing, if financed by domestic banks, can also "crowd out" the private sector by reducing lending. This can have a negative consequence on growth.

¹¹ See *How to do a Debt Sustainability Analysis for Low-Income Countries*, World Bank, 2006. In fact, this ratio is for countries with medium quality of policies and institutions, as measured by the Country Policy and Institutional Assessment (CPIA).

As such, though there is the potential to raise significant resources for HIV and AIDS from additional borrowing, this report does not recommend such an option in the case of Burkina Faso.

5.8 Financing gap with alternative financing mechanisms

Drawing on the above, it is possible to examine the total resources available for HIV. This is achieved by combining the baseline resources calculated above with the innovative sources discussed in this section. For the reasons outlined above, new borrowing and social health insurance are not included in the total.

Table 5.23 Total Resources and Financing Gap for HIV/AIDS 2008 – 2020 (CFAF Billions)

	Baseline Total	Internal mainstreaming	External mainstreaming	Workplace Programs	Airtime tax	Flight tax	Decentralisation	Total Resources
2008	25.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.2
2009	27.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.3
2010	27.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.8
2011	28.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.4
2012	29.1	0.9	0.9	0.1	4.2	2.3	0.3	37.8
2013	29.8	2.0	2.1	0.1	4.5	2.4	0.4	41.3
2014	30.6	3.2	3.4	0.1	5.0	2.6	0.4	45.2
2015	31.5	3.4	3.6	0.1	5.6	2.7	0.4	47.4
2016	32.5	3.7	3.9	0.1	6.3	2.9	0.5	49.9
2017	33.5	4.0	4.2	0.1	7.2	3.1	0.5	52.6
2018	34.7	4.3	4.5	0.1	8.2	3.2	0.5	55.6
2019	35.9	4.6	4.9	0.1	9.2	3.4	0.6	58.8
2020	37.2	5.0	5.3	0.1	10.2	3.6	0.6	62.0

The innovative sources grow in importance over time, starting at CFAF 8.7 billion in 2012 and reaching CFAF 24.8 billion by 2020. Over this nine year period, the new sources account for an additional CFAF 155.6 billion.

Figure 5.3 Resource Needs and Available Resources – Baseline plus Innovative Sources, 2008 - 2020

There is a corresponding effect on the financing gap. The small gap that was identified in Section 4 above is closed and the resources now exceed the required amount. This is illustrated in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4 Financing Gap – Baseline and Innovative Sources, 2008 - 2020

6 Efficiency

When looking into whether countries are getting value for money for their HIV/AIDS spending, it is useful to consider two types of efficiency: allocative efficiency, which looks at the degree to which resources are channelled towards the highest impact activities, and technical efficiency, which looks at whether resources have been used to deliver services of a given level of quality at the lowest possible cost.

6.1 Allocative Efficiency

While there is an increasing body of evidence indicating the types of interventions that are likely to yield the greatest results per dollar spent, many countries continue to channel resources towards interventions that are not cost-effective and in some cases have very little overall impact. Even countries at a similar level of income per capita and with similar prevalence rates demonstrate very different spending patterns, which suggests that there is scope to improve the allocative efficiency among some of these.

One of the principle reasons for this misallocation of funding relates to the unavailability of key data. While a number of costing studies have been carried out, the data from these are not always transferable across countries. Furthermore, studies that have been carried out are often contradictory leaving policy makers confused about which approach to take. Another important reason why funds are not always allocated towards the most cost effective intervention is that these interventions are politically sensitive and politicians fear backlash if, for example, they are seen to be in support of stigmatised risk groups such as commercial sex workers and injecting drug users.

Countries with low prevalence rates tend to channel larger proportions of their HIV/AIDS funds towards prevention activities since their burden of treatment is not as high as countries of higher prevalence. Burkina Faso, which has a relatively low prevalence rate compared to other Sub-Saharan African countries, has until recently been spending more on treatment than prevalence in spite of the large reduction in cost of first line ARV medication. Figure 6.1 shows that while the amount spent on treatment fell significantly between 2005 and 2006, it rose steadily in the following three years. The amount spent on prevention on the other hand fluctuated from year to year while the amount spent on management and administration of programmes remained constant at about 20% of total resources spent each year.

Figure 6.1 Expenditure by HIV/AIDS intervention, 2005 - 2008

According to the recently developed Strategic Framework on the fight Against HIV, AIDS and STIs (2011 – 2015), which outlines the overall strategic orientation of the national HIV/AIDS response, increased priority is now being placed on prevention. Figure 6.5 which summarises the resource requirements to implement this strategic framework over the coming five years shows that planned expenditure on preventative interventions is due to increase in absolute terms and as a proportion of total spending while the proportion of expenditure going towards treatment is set to fall.

Figure 6.2 Resource needs for the implementation of the Strategic Framework on the Fight Against HIV/AIDS (2011 – 2015)

6.2 Technical Efficiency

Technical efficiency refers to the delivery of a given output using the minimum number inputs. So in the case of the HIV/AIDS response this means achieving any set of specified results, such as people treated with ARVs or number of people who have received Voluntary Counselling and Testing (VCT) at the lowest cost.

A recent study carried out by Zeng *et al* used data envelop analysis (DEA) to evaluate the technical efficiency of national HIV/AIDS programmes in low and middle income countries (Zeng *et al* 2009). Using data on inputs (national HIV/AIDS expenditure) and outputs (HIV/AIDS services, namely PMTCT, VCT and ARV), the DEA methodology allows to determine a production frontier for HIV and AIDS services against which less efficient countries can be benchmarked. The study can be seen as a landmark study because its results indicate at country level the extent to which efficiency gains can be made. This information is, obviously, of crucial importance to any approach to sustainable financing for HIV and AIDS. In the paragraphs below we run through Zeng's most important findings and apply them to the case of Burkina Faso.

The study determines technical efficiency levels for different country AIDS programmes. National AIDS Spending Assessments (NASA) compiled by UNAIDS were used to determine the inputs for national HIV/AIDS programs. The number of people receiving voluntary counseling and testing (VCT), the number of HIV+ pregnant women receiving

HIV/AIDS treatment for prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT), and the number of patients receiving antiretroviral treatment (ART) were selected as programme outputs. The final data set covers 68 countries with 151 observations, spanning the years from 2002 through 2007.

In a first stage the authors used output-oriented data envelopment analysis (DEA), a classic approach to evaluating technical efficiency to estimate the efficiency of national HIV/AIDS programs. The efficiency score from output-oriented DEA models is a ratio of the current level of weighted outputs to its potential level if the country performed optimally. Considering the limitation that the conventional CCR DEA model does not incorporate prior knowledge of the relative importance of inputs and outputs in estimating weights, the authors used the DEA model with an assurance region (AR), setting weight boundaries for the outputs.

In a second stage the authors attempted to explain efficiency differentials and identified indicators on governance, health financing mechanisms, HIV/AIDS prevalence, and economic and demographic characteristics of a country as potential determinants of the technical efficiency of the program. After obtaining the efficiency scores from the pooled output-oriented DEA model, a random-effects Tobit regression model with finite population adjustment was used to explore the determinants of the efficiency of HIV/AIDS programs. The Tobit model was built on 120 observations in 2006 only because of data restrictions.

When evaluating the efficiency of the AIDS response by year, of all 151 observations, 18 are on the production frontier with efficiency scores of 100%. The high performers include countries that have been recognized for their successful HIV/AIDS programs including Thailand, Brazil, and Rwanda, which further validates the methodology used. The overall average efficiency was 49.8% (standard deviation 31.2%), indicating that, on average, the countries could have doubled their outputs if they used money as efficiently as their comparison peers in the same year.

Figure 7.3 illustrates the results more intuitively by plotting them into a two-dimension graph by standardizing the weight for PMTCT and VCT relative to ART¹². There are six countries with 100% efficiency on the production frontier, and there are 17 countries above the median efficiency of 40% but below 100%.

¹² The authors standardized the relative weight assigned to each output by averaging the corresponding relative weights from the DEA model across observations, setting the weight for ART as 1, for PMTCT as 0.10 and for VCT as 0.01.

Figure 6.3 HIV/AIDS production frontier 2002-2007

A notable result from the pooled DEA analysis (country observations from all years are pooled) is that efficiency of AIDS responses increases significantly over time, from 13.3% before 2004 (including 2004) to 47.7% in 2007¹³. This is shown in the graph below.

¹³ Data compiled from 68 low and middle income countries from 2002 to 2007. Each point represents the mean efficiency in a given year.

Figure 6.4 Change in efficiency of national HIV/AIDS programs over time (2002-2007)

This finding then throws up the question what drives efficiency of HIV/AIDS programmes. The authors consider a series of variables and verify the extent to which they impact on the efficiency scores. The table in Annex D shows the statistically significant results, their level of significance, and their contribution in explaining efficiency (size of coefficient). The most important explanatory variables¹⁴ are:

- Income measured as log [GNI/cap], with a negative value for the square of this variable
- An interaction effect between ‘control of corruption’ and ‘rule of law’
- Voice and accountability

The determinant ‘income’ (and the negative value for its square) indicates that countries’ AIDS responses become more efficient when they become richer up to a point, and then become less efficient again (the path has an inverted U-shape). The authors suggest that this is because poor countries reap off efficiency gains by augmenting their service delivery infrastructure but then at some point (the turning point of the curve) shift focus on quality of service while service delivery workers (mainly health workers) earn comparatively higher salaries, leading to a decrease in efficiency. This otherwise plausible explanation also points at one of the limitations of the approach, as quality of the AIDS programmes is not taken into account.

¹⁴ The variable ‘Voice and accountability’, measures “the degree to which citizens participating in government affairs, and freedom of expression, freedom of association and a free media”; the variable ‘Rule of law’ measures “the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society” and ‘Control of corruption’ refers to “the extent to which public power is exercised for private gain”. These variables are obtained from World Bank databases.

The positive interaction term 'control of corruption' with 'rule of law' indicates that both measures work together in contributing to efficient AIDS programmes. This findings suggest that the more the rule of law is respected and the more public power is exercised for the benefit of the public good, the more efficient AIDS programmes are implemented.

The significance of 'Voice and accountability' is likely to reflect that higher levels of beneficiary group participation in decision making lead to better value for money in the production of VCT, PMTCT and ART services. This finding is in line with best practice guidance from UNAIDS.

Not surprisingly all year dummies are significant as well suggesting that specific events in each year, and which are not captured in the other variables, explain the efficiency differential as well.

While the Zeng study is significant far beyond its application in this study, its insights directly contributes to this work in that it shows the scope for efficiency gains in Burkina Faso, and provides some indications about how better efficiency can be achieved. However, before we apply the study results to the case of Burkina Faso, we report some of the limitations of the approach. First, the study takes into account one input (expenditure) and three outputs (VCT, PMTCT, ART), which obviously is a simplification of the research question motivated by lack of available data. The study results are in that sense indicative and the underlying assumption is that the efficiency levels found for the production of VCT, PMTCT and ART apply to other programme interventions as well. Second, technical efficiency, which is studied here, is not the only relevant criterion to assess an AIDS response. AIDS programmes may, for example, be most effective while not being fully efficient. Third, some evident drivers related to the management and structure of the AIDS response, including the cost of ARV, are not taken into account when examining the drivers of efficiency. Last, as indicated before, abstraction is made of the quality of the services provided. These limitations must be taken into account when assessing the results for Burkina Faso below.

6.3 Technical efficiency in Burkina Faso

The graph below shows the efficiency score for Burkina Faso over the years 2003 to 2007 (with 2004 missing) and compares this with the average values in the sample of 68 countries (Zeng, 2010). In 2003 the technical efficiency of Burkina's AIDS programme was comparable to the average of all countries. In the following two years the efficiency gains in the pool of countries was much stronger than in Burkina Faso but since 2005 the growth rate in efficiency is similar in Burkina and the pool. However, Burkina Faso is now on a lower efficiency path. During the same period some countries scored 100% efficiency in selected years during this period and they serve as benchmark for all countries.

This throws up the question if the efficiency of the Response can be improved? We briefly examine management efficiency and the cost of ARV in the paragraphs below.

6.4 Management efficiency

In 2008, Management and Administration, which is defined as all administrative expenditure other than at the point of service delivery accounted for 19.8% of the total expenditure on HIV/AIDS with most of this coming from external sources (77%). While this represents a small fall in the share of funds spent on management and administration from the 2007 levels which stood at 20.4%, in absolute terms the quantity of resources spent on management and administration increased by 16%.

Figure 6.5 Breakdown of Expenditure on HIV by Intervention in 2008

Source: NASA 2008

Within the overall management and administration category, expenditure on Planning, Coordination and Management of HIV/AIDS programmes is by far the biggest expenditure item accounting for 64% of resources (Figure 6.6). This represents a marked increase from 2007 when only 37.2% of the resources spent on this category were spent in this area. Similarly the share of expenditure on monitoring and evaluation increased significantly across the two years from 8.8% in 2007 to 16.9% in 2008. The share of expenditure on administrative and transaction costs related to the management and disbursement of funds on the other hand reduced from 43.1% in 2007 to 10.3% in 2008. The remaining sub-categories - operational research; serosurveillance; surveillance of HIV drug resistance; drug supply systems; Information Technology (IT); supervision by staff and patient monitoring; and rehabilitation and construction of facilities - together only account for 9% of funds spent in 2008, down from 11.7% in 2007.

Figure 6.6 Expenditure on Management and Administration by sub-category

Source: NASA 2008

The table below provides figures for the proportion of total AIDS expenditure for Programme and management support. With a spending of 22% on Programme and management support Burkina Faso is placed in the higher regions compared to other countries. Against an average of 14% in the pool, this suggests ample room for efficiency improvement.

Table 6.1 Programme management support as a % of total AIDS expenditure, 51 countries

6.5 Drug efficiency

Treating people with antiretrovirals constitutes the single greatest cost to the HIV/AIDS response in many low income countries. This is true in spite of the historic reductions in the cost of first line ARV medication from over \$10,000 to roughly \$175 per person per year. While this has resulted in significant improvements in the affordability of these drugs and an increase in treatment coverage from 7% to 42% between 2003 and 2008, the continued high cost of second line treatment means that most low income countries fall far short of meeting their target ART coverage, which many have now set at about 80% of those in need¹⁵.

A number of global strategies are currently being implemented to reduce the cost of antiretroviral medicines. These include the following:

1. Pooled procurement arrangements. This mechanism is designed to group multiple purchasers into a single purchasing unit in the hope that an increase in

¹⁵ <http://www.avert.org/universal-access.htm>

purchasing volumes will lead to economies of scale. The Global Fund is currently operating this kind of arrangement.

2. Third-party price negotiations. This was first introduced by the Clinton Foundation HIV/AIDS Initiative (CHAI) in 2003. How it operates is that CHAI negotiates a price ceiling with suppliers of generic ARVs and based on this, all member countries of the CHAI procurement consortium are entitled to purchase drugs from these suppliers at a price less than or equal to the CHAI negotiated price.
3. Differential pricing. This strategy, which is applied only to branded ARVs, is used to link ARV prices with affordability by applying a lower prices for ARV medication for low and middle income countries. The criteria for grouping countries are determined by the manufacturer, usually based on income level and prevalence rates.
4. The Doha declaration and TRIPS flexibilities. As of June 2010, 17 low and middle income countries have benefited from TRIPS flexibilities, making low cost generic ARVs available to their populations [0]. Other low and middle income countries have until 2016 to make use of TRIPS flexibilities to scale up treatment access.
5. Patent pooling. The UNITAID Executive Board adopted a patent pooling initiative in December 2009 whereby ARV patents are brought together on a voluntary basis and made available non-exclusively to generic manufacturers in exchange for royalty payments to patent holders.

Unfortunately, not all of these strategies have achieved the desired results. A recent study for example found that the association between purchase volume and price for 19 out of the 24 dosages included in the study were not statistically significant suggesting that increases in purchasing volumes has not necessarily resulted in lower ARV prices [0]. With regards to differential pricing, a study by Medicins Sans Frontieres (MSF) showed that in practice there are a number of barriers preventing eligible countries from purchasing ARV medicines at a differential price such as the manufacturer not marketing the drugs in their country. In cases where the drugs are available for purchase, the study found that even the differential prices, particularly for *second-line* medications were extremely high [0].

Using data from the Global Price Reporting Mechanism (GPRM)¹⁶ and summary report of this data compiled by the WHO [0] we compared the annual treatment cost per patient for 10 selected *first-line* ARV medicines to the transaction price per patient per year among 45 low income countries. The ARV medicines used in our analysis include all those in the summary report for which there is also data available for Burkina Faso. Figure 6.7 shows that the annual treatment cost per patient in Burkina Faso is higher than the median transaction price for most of the selected first line ARVs, with only one, Efavirenz (EFV), showing a lower than median cost. That said however, the price differential is not huge in most cases and Tenofovir (TDF) + Emtricitabine (FTC) + Efavirenz (EFV), which is by

¹⁶ <http://www.who.int/hiv/amds/price/hdd/>

far the most expensive treatment included here, is in fact the same price in Burkina Faso as the median price for LICs. More details are in Annex B and C.

Figure 6.7 Comparison of the median price of selected first line ARVS in low income countries to the treatment cost in Burkina Faso

Source: Data taken from <http://www.who.int/hiv/amds/price/hdd/> and the WHO Summary Report from the Global Price Report Mechanism 2008, accessed from: <http://www.who.int/hiv/amds/gprm/en/>

Applying the same methodology as above, our analysis of *second-line* ARVs shows that out of the seven treatment types included, the price of five are considerably higher in Burkina compared to the median prices in the 45 other low income countries. In the case of Abacavir (ABC) 300 mg the price in Burkina is almost three times the median price, for Ritonavir (RTV) 100 mg it is more than double and for the other three, the price in Burkina is roughly 30% more than the median price. As for the treatment types that have a lower price in Burkina, Didanosine (ddl 100 mg) and Indinavir (IDV 400 mg), both are only marginally cheaper than the median price (0.05% and 3.6% cheaper respectively).

Figure 6.8 Comparison of the median price of selected *second-line* ARVS in low income countries to the treatment cost in Burkina Faso

These findings would suggest that there is scope to reduce the prices of ARVs in Burkina Faso, particularly in the case of *second-line* medication. It may be worth exploring the potential of drawing more on some of the international strategies for reducing ARV costs or in cases where these strategies are being used but are not working, to investigate the reasons for this.

6.6 Efficiency gains projection

If the country would have achieved full efficiency in 2008, then three times as many AIDS services would have been produced; or the same level of services could have been achieved with three times less resources. The level of technical efficiency of the AIDS response in Burkina Faso, at 22% in 2008, suggests there is important room for improvement. ARV can be bought more cheaply, however, there doesn't seem to be much room for improvement at this level.

In the remainder of this analysis we assume that Burkina Faso will be able to bring the AIDS Response to the current production frontier (100%) in 10 years time. As simultaneously during this period service delivery technology will improve, and thus even higher levels of efficiency could be achieved, this seems to be a reasonable hypothesis. Practically we assume that efficiency gains will first have further improved to 52.5% in 2010, and will then further improve at a slower rate to achieve 95% in 2020. This trend is pictured in the graph below.

Figure 6.9 Efficiency gains projection in Burkina Faso

6.6.2 AIDS financing gap with efficiency gains

We can now also revisit the AIDS financing gap and consider resource needs with efficiency gains. This is shown in the graph below.

Table 6.2 HIV/AIDS financing gap with efficiency gains, % GDP

The situation with efficiency gains is completely different from the one without efficiency gains. That is because the potential gains are significant: the same output can be

realised with about only half the financial resources. When efficiency gains materialise in the short run, this scenario suggests that the AIDS financing gap will be modest only, and turn positive by 2012 already, especially in combination with additional resources from innovative sources of funding.

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7 Sensitivity Analysis

In this section, we consider the implications of changing some of the assumptions shown above. As international flows currently represent such a large proportion of the resources, we consider different scenarios for these flows in the future. We go on to look at changing the key macroeconomic assumptions.

7.1 External HIV and AIDS flows

Since donor financing constitutes a large part of HIV/AIDS financing in Burkina Faso, we look at two alternative international financing scenarios. Under scenario 1, a more pessimistic scenario, we assume donor financing to decrease by 2% on an annual basis in US Dollar terms until 2020. Under the second scenario we assume a more optimistic outlook with donor financing increasing by 2% on an annual basis in US Dollar terms up to 2020.

Figure 7.1 shows the implications of the changes for both the baseline and innovative sources scenarios. Whilst the scenarios show that there is some degree of variation in the financing gap, the difference is relatively minor and the general trend in each case is maintained. Nevertheless, it serves as an important reminder of the inherent uncertainties in extrapolating so far into the future. This is particularly the case with the macroeconomic variables, as we shall see in the following section.

Figure 7.1 HIV/AIDS Financing Gap as % of GDP – Alternative Scenarios for External Flows

7.2 Macroeconomic Assumptions

Equally important for the projections are the macroeconomic assumptions that underpin them. It is clearly not possible to accurately determine the level of GDP in 10 years time and the long run growth rate used in this analysis is simply an average of recent (5 year) economic performance. In this section, we consider the implications of changing that assumption.

Again, we present a pessimistic and an optimistic scenario. In the pessimistic scenario, real GDP growth is one percentage point lower in every year than in the main scenarios presented above. In the optimistic scenario, real GDP growth is one percentage point higher in every year. Note that these effects are shown independent of the scenarios for external flows presented above (i.e. we return to the main assumption for external flows and do not combine these new assumptions with the pessimistic and optimistic assumptions for external flows above).

Figure 7.2 HIV/AIDS Financing Gap as % of GDP – Alternative Macroeconomic Scenarios

Figure 7.2 shows the impact of the pessimistic and optimistic scenarios on both the baseline case and the case where innovative sources have been added to the baseline. Surprisingly, the change in the assumptions does not appear to make a significant difference. There are a number of reasons for this.

First, the chart shows the financing gap, rather than the level of available resources. Even when we include significant new flows for HIV from the increase in general taxation, as discussed in Section 7.1 above, a large part of the available resources

continues to come from external sources. These flows are unaffected by changes in GDP.

Second, the financing gap is shown as a percentage of GDP. Therefore, whilst a reduction in GDP may reduce the available resources in absolute terms, there is also an effect on GDP itself meaning the denominator is smaller. Hence, the ratio of the two may not be changed significantly.

Finally, the different macroeconomic assumptions do not take effect until 2014 (as the IMF assumptions are retained until 2013). Therefore, the cumulative effect by 2020 is relatively modest.

A further source of uncertainty in these projections is the exchange rate. A change in the exchange rate will affect the value of the external resources (in CFAF terms). However, the impact on the financing gap is not easy to determine, as some of the resource needs will be imported (e.g. drugs) and as such will be denominated in foreign currency. Ultimately, how a change in the exchange rate will affect the financing gap will depend on the relative proportions of external resources in the available resources and imports in the resource needs.

There is insufficient information to be able to accurately carry out such an analysis, but it serves as a further reminder of the uncertainties inherent in extrapolating financial flows so far into the future.

Table 7.1 Worst and best case scenario

Throughout the text we have presented a number of possible scenarios. In order to give an idea which is the likely under and upper limit of the AIDS financing gap, we calculate the gap in the worst possible scenario, which is without efficiency gains, no additional sources of funding, slower than expected economic growth and declining donor resources.

8 Conclusion

This study set out to examine the AIDS financing gap in Burkina Faso to 2020. The AIDS financing gap is the difference between estimated resource need and resource availability.

Under a baseline scenario, which applies conservative assumptions to current levels of resource need and resource availability, we found that the financing gap stands at 0.18% in 2010 to gradually decline to 0.1% in 2020. This suggests that relatively modest increases in resources from existing sources for AIDS expenditure can fill this gap. However, given that the resource needs and available resources are calculated separately it is not guaranteed that the available resources will be targeted at the needs as identified as some revenue sources will be earmarked for certain areas (prevention, research, treatment, management, etc.) and activities (ARVs, workplace programmes, IEC, etc.). Increases in resources to fill the AIDS financing gap must therefore go hand in hand with careful resource allocation planning.

We then estimated the resources that can be generated through alternative sources of funding. These are sources that are not currently tapped into and that generate resources additional to the current ones. We considered public sector mainstreaming and decentralisation, increased contributions from the private sector, a tax on airtime and a levy on international passenger air travel. We find that taken together these alternative sources have a potential to generate CFA 24.8 billion in 2020, or about 19 times the AIDS financing gap in that year.

We also quantify the effect of including ARV into the benefit package of the Social Health Insurance the Government considers to set up and find that further research would be needed to assess whether the additional premium would be affordable by the majority of the targeted membership of the scheme. We find that there is some room for additional borrowing to address the HIV epidemic. However, because it is uncertain when the SHI will be set up, and because additional borrowing would be the option 'of last resort' we don't carry these results further into the analysis.

Lastly, we examine the efficiency of the Burkina Faso AIDS response to see whether more savings can be made. We found evidence that Burkina's AIDS service delivery framework is only 1/3 as efficient as the most efficient countries in 2007. Although it is likely that efficiency has improved further since 2007, we estimate that significant, up to 50%, efficiency gains can be made between 2010 and 2017.

Overall our analysis shows an encouraging picture suggesting that Burkina Faso, under the assumption that external donors maintain their current contributions in nominal terms, the same share of government resources are allocated to AIDS expenditure, together with a small share of funds from alternative sources, and, or combined with efficiency gains, can bridge the AIDS financing gap.

However, resource needs and gap estimates change over time in light of new information and changes to the structure and scale of interventions. The findings of this study are therefore but a starting point for discussion among the key stakeholders on the validity of resource needs requirements and the different paths to covering any financing gap.

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Annex A Overview of the Macroeconomic Framework

A.1 Introduction

The macroeconomic approach adopts a numeric framework, known as a financial programming framework, which is designed to assist in the development of a consistent approach to the different aspects of economic policy. The key feature of the financial programming framework is that it is based on a comprehensive view of the national economy, comprising four inter-dependent sectors. The four sectors are:

- The Real Sector, which relates to productive activities of the economy.
- The Fiscal Sector, which captures government transactions.
- The External Sector, which includes all transactions between the country in question and other countries.
- The Monetary Sector, which includes the transactions of the banking system and of the central bank.

Whilst not a sector in its own right, attention is also given to the debt of the central government, as the stocks and flows of the government's debt are reflected in the fiscal, external and monetary sectors.

At the outset, it should be clearly understood that the macroeconomic framework is not an economic model. It does not constitute a set of equations which attempt to model the behaviour and interaction between different sets of economic agents. In economic terminology, it is not based on a set of econometrically estimated behavioral and/or structural relationships which drive economic outcomes.

The macroeconomic framework is a tool for ensuring the consistency between different sets of assumptions about the future course of the economy. In other words, by starting with a set of assumptions about the economy (e.g. GDP growth), the framework assesses the impact of different policy options on the four sectors of the economy in a consistent manner.

A.2 Key Components

The starting point for the macroeconomic framework is the tables published on the country's macroeconomic performance by the IMF. These tables are produced in a standard format for all countries as part of the IMF's Article IV surveillance activities. The standard IMF documents include five tables that are replicated in the macroeconomic framework used for this analysis. These are:

- Table 1: Selected Economic Indicators, containing summary data from the real, fiscal, monetary and external sectors.
- Tables 2 & 3: Fiscal Operations of Central Government, describing the government budget and its financing.

-
- Table 4: Monetary Accounts, showing the paths of broad money, net foreign assets and net domestic assets.
 - Table 5: Balance of Payments, including indicators on gross international reserves.

These tables are transposed into Excel and expanded further as necessary, to produce data for the four sectors of the economy described above. This is done through the following six work sheets:

- **Overview:** The Overview sheet includes projections for headline macroeconomic variables such as real GDP growth, GDP deflator and the exchange rate.
- **Real:** The Real sheet provides the projections of the real sector, including values for GDP and its components (including consumption and investment).
- **Fiscal:** The Fiscal sheet provides information on the annual budget for the Government, including projections for domestic revenue, expenditure, grants and deficit financing.
- **Money:** The Money sheet provides projections for the monetary sector. It includes the path of key monetary aggregates, such as credit to the private sector.
- **External:** The External sheet provides forecasts for the Balance of Payments, including projections for imports, exports, and gross international reserves.
- **Debt:** Whilst the Debt sheet does not reflect a sector as such, it performs a simple function by taking the debt disbursements, combining these with the existing debt stock and forecast repayments, to project the debt variables into the future.

The different sheets are all linked to each other to ensure consistency, as discussed further below. Additional worksheets are used to group together the key macroeconomic assumptions, to include the data on HIV and AIDS resources and to present charts of macroeconomic indicators.

A.3 Theoretical Approach

The framework uses four macroeconomic accounting identities to ensure consistency between the different sectors of the economy. A macroeconomic accounting identity is a relationship between a set of economic variables that must hold true by definition. For example, GDP must be equal to the sum of its components (investment, consumption, imports and exports). Each sector has its own accounting identity.

The framework ensures consistency between the sectors in two ways. Firstly, the macroeconomic framework ensures that all of the accounting identities are met. It does this through the use of a “residual” item, which is set via a formula to ensure that the identity is always true. For example, if we have already determined GDP, investment, imports and exports, then there can only be one value for consumption

that is consistent with the accounting identity for the real sector (i.e. Consumption = GDP – Investment – Exports + Imports). In this case, consumption is known as the “residual”.

Secondly, the macroeconomic framework ensures that wherever a variable features in more than one sector, the projections for that variable are the same in both sectors. For example, Imports features in both the real sector (as a component of GDP) and the external sector (as a component of the Current Account). Thus, the macroeconomic framework will ensure that whatever values are used for Imports in the external sector are also used in the real sector.

A.3.1 Macroeconomic Accounting Identities

This section will examine the accounting identities used in each sector and the residual that is used to balance them.

The Real Sector

Basic Identity:

$$GDP = \text{Consumption (Private + Public)} + \text{Investment (Private + Public)} + \text{Exports} - \text{Imports}$$

Residual:

Private Consumption

The primary assumption in this sector is that of growth in real GDP. This is used to extrapolate the current figure for GDP into the coming years. An assumption is also made about the future path of the GDP deflator in order to convert between real GDP and nominal GDP.

Having determined the value of GDP in future years, it is necessary to determine its composition. Public consumption (i.e. government current expenditure) and public investment (i.e. government development expenditure) are determined by the Fiscal sheet (see below). By making assumptions about the share of investment in GDP, it is possible to produce forecast figures for investment. Finally, Imports and Exports are linked from the External sheet (see below).

Therefore, having determined the total value for GDP and all but one of its components, the residual component must be set to ensure consistency with the basic accounting identity. In this case, private consumption is used as the residual and is equal to GDP plus imports, less exports, private investment and total government spending.

The Fiscal Sector

Basic Identity:

Total Revenue – Total Expenditure = Net Borrowing

Residual:

Net Disbursements of Domestic Debt

This sector is focused on the government budget. Firstly, tax revenue is determined (based on an assumption about its share of GDP) as well other sources of revenue, such as grants and non-tax revenue. External grants are converted to local currency using the exchange rate.

Assumptions are made about the government's expenditure (excluding debt service). The interest payments on debt are calculated in the Debt sheet, such that a higher deficit in one year is reflected in higher interest payments in the subsequent year. These factors determine the government's overall deficit and hence the government's borrowing requirement. Future disbursements and principal repayments on external debt are determined by assumption and converted to local currency using the exchange rate.

All that remains is to determine the net disbursements on domestic debt. This is the residual in this sector and it set at a level to balance government borrowing with the overall deficit.

The Monetary Sector

Basic Identity:

Net Foreign Assets + Net Domestic Assets = Broad Money

Residual:

Net Claims on Other Sectors (a component of Net Domestic Assets)

Net foreign assets are determined by the net flow of foreign currency into the country, which is given by the change in official reserves in the balance of payments (i.e. from the External sheet).

Net domestic assets includes net claims on government and net claims on other sectors (i.e. the private sector). Net claims on government is determined by the outstanding stock of government debt, which is taken directly from the Debt sheet. Net claims on other sectors is the residual in this sector and therefore calculated at the end.

Broad money can derived from the economic relationship between nominal GDP, broad money and the velocity of money ($PY=vM$). Broad money is therefore calculated by dividing nominal GDP by an assumed figure for the velocity of money.

Having determined everything else using the above assumptions, net claims on other sectors is the residual and is set to ensure compliance with the accounting identity for this sector. It is equal to broad money less net foreign assets and less net claims on government.

The External Sector

<p><u>Basic Identity:</u></p> $\text{Current Account} + \text{Capital Account} + \text{Financial Account} + \text{Errors \& Omissions} = \text{Change in Official Reserve Assets}$ <p><u>Residual:</u></p> $\text{Change in Official Reserve Assets}$

The external sector is essentially a representation of the balance of payments, which captures the flow of foreign currency into and out of the country in question. The current account is determined by assumptions about the import and export of goods and services, income and remittances. Also included in the current account are government interest payments on external debt (taken from the Debt sheet) and external budget support grants (taken from the Fiscal sheet).

The capital account includes external project grants (taken from the Fiscal sheet). The financial account requires assumptions about foreign direct investment and portfolio investment. The only other significant components of the financial account are the disbursements and repayments of external loans to government, which are taken from assumptions in the Fiscal sheet.

Errors and omissions are assumed to be zero in the future. The only item left is the change in official reserve assets, which is used as the residual to ensure consistency in this sheet. The change in official reserves is therefore given by the sum of the current account, the capital account and the financial account.

A.3.2 Key Linkages between the Sectors

As discussed above, the second source of consistency comes from the use of only one set of forecasts wherever a variable appears in two different sectors. Table 1 summarises the linkages between different sheets. It is important to note that the link is created from the sheet listed on the left hand side to the sheet list along the top of the table (i.e. imports from the External sheet are transferred to the Real sheet.) To avoid confusion, only the most important linkages are shown, these correspond with the linkages discussed in the text above.

Table 1: Key Inter-Sector Linkages in the Macroeconomic Framework

To From	Real	Fiscal	Debt	Money	External
Real		GDP (for Revenue projections)		GDP (for Broad Money projections)	
Fiscal	Government Spending		Net Disbursements on Domestic Debt Disbursements on External Debt		External Grants Disbursements on External Debt
Debt		Interest Payments Principal Repayments on External Debt		Debt Stock (for Net Domestic Assets)	Interest on External Debt Principal Repayments on External Debt
Money					
External	Imports Exports		Exchange Rate	Change in Official Reserve Assets	

Using the above framework, it is possible to condense the forecasting of the economy, and its various sectors, to just a handful of key assumptions. Using these assumptions, the linkages and identities described above, and a few further details, it is possible to then project a range of macroeconomic variables and indicators into the future.

The framework therefore operates by retaining the IMF projections for the short and medium term (until 2013) and then making a number of high level assumptions for key macroeconomic variables over the long term. These assumptions are based upon an extrapolation of the medium term IMF projections and an analysis of the available information on the economy of the country in question.

A.4 Incorporating HIV and AIDS Resources

HIV and AIDS resources can be divided into two forms; revenues and expenditures. It is important to be clear on the distribution to avoid double-counting the resources. For example, a grant from a donor would be included as a revenue but may also be counted as an expenditure by the government. Table 9.1 shows the HIV and AIDS resources incorporated into the macroeconomic framework and the sectors that they are linked directly to.

Table 8.1 HIV and AIDS Resource Flows in the Macroeconomic Framework

Resource Flow	Sector Linkages
<i>Revenues</i>	
External project grants included in the budget	Fiscal, External
External project grants not included in the budget	None
External project loans	Fiscal, External, (Debt)
Tax and non-tax revenues collected by the government and earmarked for HIV and AIDS	Fiscal
Domestic borrowing by the government and earmarked for HIV and AIDS	Fiscal, (Debt)
<i>Expenditures</i>	
Government (Current) Expenditure	Fiscal
Expenditure by external project grants not included in the budget	None
Expenditure by private individuals and companies	Real

These resources are integrated into the appropriate sectors of the macroeconomic framework. This ensures consistency in both the macroeconomic projections and the HIV expenditure projections in two ways.

First, those resources that are determined exogenously (either through external factors or by policy decisions) are linked to the macroeconomic framework so that changes in these variables have a macroeconomic impact. For example, higher grants from external donors may (i) increase government expenditure in the fiscal sector and (ii) increase the change in official reserves in the external sector (amongst other effects). Equally, a decision to increase taxes to finance HIV will (i) increase the deficit and domestic borrowing and (ii) by higher interest payments on that debt, further increase the deficit in future years (again amongst other effects).

Second, HIV and AIDS resources can be linked to macroeconomic variables to model their size under different scenarios. For example, external grants and loans will be converted into local currency via the exchange rate and domestic resources can be linked to GDP growth to see how they change under different scenarios.

Using the framework above, it is then possible to insert different assumptions for key macroeconomic variables and different HIV and AIDS financing mechanisms to examine scenarios for HIV and AIDS expenditure into the future. These scenarios can be supported by various indicators to assess the plausibility of the scenario (e.g. is the share of HIV/AIDS expenditure of GDP excessive?) and its macroeconomic stability (e.g. is government debt sustainable? Is the balance of payments stable?).

Annex B Incorporating ARV into the Social Health Insurance project in Burkina Faso: overview table

year	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Population size											
Population	15,730,977	16,248,558	16,779,206	17,322,796	17,880,386	18,450,494	19,034,397	19,632,147	20,244,080	20,870,060	21,510,181
Household size	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3	5.3
Number of households	2,968,109	3,065,766	3,165,888	3,268,452	3,373,658	3,481,225	3,591,396	3,704,179	3,819,638	3,937,747	4,058,525
Number of dependants	12,762,868	13,182,792	13,613,318	14,054,344	14,506,728	14,969,269	15,443,001	15,927,968	16,424,442	16,932,313	17,451,656
Proportion of dependants (%)	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.81
Children 0 - 15 years	7,917,389	8,180,966	8,443,253	8,703,685	8,963,035	9,219,363	9,473,168	9,723,983	9,972,237	10,435,030	10,755,091
Children 0 - 15 years (% of total population)	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	49%	<u>50%</u>	<u>50%</u>
Population structure											
Public sector (2.0%)	314,620	324,971	335,584	346,456	357,608	369,010	380,688	392,643	404,882	417,401	430,204
Pensioners (0.5%)	78,655	81,243	83,896	86,614	89,402	92,252	95,172	98,161	101,220	104,350	107,551
Private sector (4.6%)	723,625	747,434	771,843	796,849	822,498	848,723	875,582	903,079	931,228	960,023	989,468
Informal sector (92.9%)	14,614,078	15,094,910	15,587,882	16,092,877	16,610,879	17,140,509	17,682,955	18,238,265	18,806,750	19,388,286	19,982,958
Total	15,730,977	16,248,558	16,779,206	17,322,796	17,880,386	18,450,494	19,034,397	19,632,147	20,244,080	20,870,060	21,510,181
Coverage scenario SHI (%)											
Public sector	0	0	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Pensioners	0	0	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Private sector	0	0	50	<u>65</u>	80	<u>90</u>	100	100	100	100	100
Informal sector	0	0	5	<u>18</u>	30	<u>45</u>	60	<u>67</u>	<u>73</u>	80	<u>90</u>

Note: figures underlined are linear extrapolations

Coverage scenario SHI	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Public sector	0	0	335,584	346,456	357,608	369,010	380,688	392,643	404,882	417,401	430,204
Pensioners	0	0	83,896	86,614	89,402	92,252	95,172	98,161	101,220	104,350	107,551
Private sector	0	0	385,922	517,952	657,998	763,850	875,582	903,079	931,228	960,023	989,468
Informal sector	0	0	779,394	2,816,254	4,983,264	7,713,229	10,609,773	12,158,843	13,791,617	15,510,629	17,984,662
Total	0	0	1,584,796	3,767,275	6,088,271	8,938,342	11,961,215	13,552,725	15,228,947	16,992,403	19,511,885
Population in need of ARV (%)											
Adults	0.002048	0.002294	0.002310	0.002299	0.002336	0.002354	0.002448	0.002500	0.002554	0.002609	0.002666
Children	0.002048	0.002294	0.002310	0.002299	0.002336	0.002354	0.002448	0.002500	0.002554	0.002609	0.002666
Population in need of ARV											
Adults	16,005	18,511	19,264	19,822	20,837	21,739	23,406	24,779	26,243	27,235	28,676
Children	16,218	18,771	19,511	20,016	20,944	21,711	23,190	24,318	25,477	27,235	28,676
Total	32,223	37,281	38,775	39,838	41,781	43,451	46,596	49,097	51,720	54,470	57,352
SHI population in need of ARV											
Adult	0	0	1819	4311	7095	10532	14708	17106	19741	22175	26012
Children	0	0	1843	4353	7131	10518	14573	16788	19166	22175	26012
Total	0	0	3662	8664	14226	21050	29281	33893	38907	44349	52024
Cost of AVR per person per year (US\$)											
First line	273	240	211	185	163	143	143	143	143	143	143
Second line	713	691	669	649	628	609	609	609	609	609	609
Note: take from documents / interpolated 2009/14											

Total cost ARV in SHI population (US\$)

First	0.00	0.00	750,568	1,560,578	2,252,193	2,928,820	4,074,141	4,715,854	5,413,480	6,170,701	7,238,555
Second	0.00	0.00	66,178	151,710	241,399	346,118	481,469	557,304	639,748	729,234	855,429
Total 2.7% second line, source: RN BF	0.00	0.00	816,747	1,712,288	2,493,592	3,274,938	4,555,610	5,273,158	6,053,228	6,899,934	8,093,985

SHI overhead mark-up assumptions (in % of turn over)

			15	15	15	10	10	7	7	7	7
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Total ARV related costs in SHI (US\$)

	0.00	0.00	939,259	1,969,131	2,867,631	3,602,432	5,011,170	5,642,280	6,476,954	7,382,930	8,660,563
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Contributing members of SHI (10% informal sector exempt)

	0.00	0.00	1,506,857	3,485,650	5,589,945	8,167,019	10,900,238	12,336,841	13,849,785	15,441,340	17,713,419
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Total additional contribution per member for ARV (US\$)

	0.00	0.00	0.62	0.56	0.51	0.44	0.46	0.46	0.47	0.48	0.49
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Total additional contribution per member for ARV (XOF)

	0.00	0.00	405	367	333	287	299	297	304	311	318
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Annex C Median transaction price of first-line ARV medicines for adult treatment per patient per year (US\$ppy) for Low-income countries and Annual Treatment cost per patient in Burkina Faso in 2008

ARV (first line)	Dosage	DDD (tablets or capsule)	Median Transaction Price (US \$/ppy)			Burkina Faso Data				
			2008	2009	1st Quarter 2010	Annual Treatment Cost per Patient	Date of Order	Manufacturer	Country of manufacture	Source
Stavudine (d4T)	30 mg	2	19	19	19	32	21.04.2008	Aspen Pharmacare Ltd.	South Africa	Global Fund
Lamivudine (3TC)	150 mg	2	37	31	32	43	21.04.2008	Ranbaxy Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Nevirapine (NVP)	200 mg	2	41	39	35	53 34	21.04.2008 14.07.2008	Hetero Drugs Ltd. Hetero Drugs Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Stavudine (d4T) + Lamivudine (3TC)	30 mg + 150 mg	2	53	44	39	62 90	21.04.2008 21.04.2008	Ranbaxy Ltd. Ranbaxy Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Stavudine (d4T) + Lamivudine (3TC) + Nevirapine (NVP)	30 mg + 150 mg + 200 mg	2	88	81	64	135 106	21.04.2008 21.04.2008	Ranbaxy Ltd. Ranbaxy Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Zidovudine (ZDV)	300 mg	2	104	92	81	117	21.04.2008	Ranbaxy Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Zidovudine (ZDV) + Lamivudine (3TC)	300 mg + 150 mg	2	115	107	103	138	21.04.2008 21.04.2008	Hetero Drugs Ltd. Hetero Drugs	India	Global Fund

							08	Ltd.		
Efavirenz (EFV)	200 mg	3	186	186	164	177	20.10.2008	Aurobindo Pharma Ltd.	India	UNITAID
Efavirenz (EFV)	600 mg	1	146	83	83	142 222	14.07.2008 21.04.2008	Emcure Pharmaceuticals Ltd. Ranbaxy Ltd.	India India	Global Fund
Tenofovir (TDF)	300 mg	1	166	151	100	?	21.04.2008	Tridem Pharma	France	Global Fund
Tenofovir (TDF) + Emtricitabine (FTC) + Efavirenz (EFV)	300 mg + 200 mg + 600 mg	1	613	613	243	613	21.04.2008	Merck, Sharp & Dohme Ltd.	Denmark	Global Fund

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Annex D Median transaction price of second-line ARV medicines for adult treatment per patient per year (US\$ppy) for Low-income countries and Annual Treatment cost per patient in Burkina Faso in 2008

ARV (Second Line)	Dosage	DDD (tablets or capsules)	Median Transaction Price (US \$/ppy)			Burkina Faso Data				
			2008	2009	1st Quarter 2010	Annual Treatment Cost per Patient	Date of Order	Manufacturer	Country of manufacture	Source
Abacavir (ABC)	300 mg	2	313	280	124	927	21.04.2008	GlaxoSmithKline Ltd.	Denmark	Global Fund
Didanosine (ddI)	100 mg	4	189	188	-	188	20.10.2008	Aurobindo Pharma Ltd.	India	UNITAID
Didanosine (ddI)	250 mg	1	223	184	-	288	21.04.2008	Bristol-Myers Squibb	France	Global Fund
Didanosine (ddI)	400 mg	1	288	261	209	372	21.04.2008	Bristol-Myers Squibb	France	Global Fund
Indinavir (IDV)	400 mg	4	406	406	361	391	21.04.2008	Hetero Drugs Ltd.	India	Global Fund
Lopinavir (LPV) + Ritonavir (RTV)	200 mg + 50 mg	4	500	500	469	666	21.04.2008	Abbott Laboratories Ltd.	Germany	Global Fund
Ritonavir (RTV)	100 mg	2	84	83	-	135 258	21.04.2008	Abbott Laboratories Ltd. Abbott Laboratories Ltd.	Germany. UK and N. Ireland	Global Fund

Annex E Determinants of efficiency

Determinant (independent variable)	Coefficient	Standard Error
Voice and accountability (VA)**	0.392	0.150
Government commitment to health*	0.031	0.015
External source as percentage of total health expenditure **	0.030	0.010
Government source as percentage of total health expenditure *	-0.014	0.006
Control of corruption × Rule of Law **	0.602	0.226
Control of corruption × External share of health spending*	0.022	0.009
Log(GNI per capita)*	3.485	1.442
Square of log(GNI per capita)*	-0.207	0.093
Log (adult population)*	0.147	0.066
HIV/AIDS prevalence (in percentage points)**	0.052	0.015
Reference category: year 2002		
Year 2003**	0.485	0.160
Year 2004**	1.323	0.143
Year 2005**	1.702	0.143
Year 2006**	2.108	0.142